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Learning to Analyze what is Beyond the Visible Spectrum

Amanda Berg

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Learning to Analyze what is Beyond the Visible Spectrum

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For Olov and Alfons

POPULÄRVETENSKAPLIG SAMMANFATTNING

Sensorer som kan mäta termisk infraröd strålning över ett större område och producera en visuell bild, så kallade värmekameror, har länge använts för militärt bruk. Däremot har värmekameror inte varit lika vanliga inom civila tillämpningar, främst på grund av att de har varit dyra och utrymmeskrävande. På senare år har utvecklingen gått framåt och samtidigt som kamerorna blivit mindre och billigare har även bildkvalitén förbättrats avsevärt. Nu finns det till och med små värmekameror att fästa på eller bygga in i mobiltelefoner. I takt med att värmekamerorna har blivit mindre och billigare så har fler civila tillämpningar vuxit fram. Till exempel har det blivit vanligt att använda värmekameror i industrin, för eftersökning av försvunna personer, i säkerhetssystem i bilar, för att upptäcka bränder och i medicinska sammanhang, för att nämna några. Jämfört med kameror känsliga för synligt ljus är de fördelaktiga i många situationer eftersom de kan producera en bild i totalt mörker. Värmekameror gör inte heller lika mycket intrång på personlig integritet.

Denna avhandling behandlar området automatisk bildanalys i termiskt infraröda bilder och video. Fokus ligger på maskininlärning, en undergrupp till området artificiell intelligens. En vanlig missuppfattning är att bildanalys i termiskt infraröda bilder är identiskt med bildanalys i visuella gråskalebilder. Avhandlingen visar att föregående påstående inte alltid stämmer. Så länge en metod designad för visuella bilder inte är beroende av färgattribut kan den appliceras på termiskt infrarött, men resultaten för olika metoder har visat sig variera beroende på om de används på visuella eller termiska sekvenser. Det vill säga, olika angreppssätt fungerar olika bra i de två olika modaliteterna.

Tre olika typer av bildanalysproblem studeras i avhandlingen: visuell objektsföljning, anomalidetektion, och övergångar mellan två olika modaliteter. Det bedrivs mycket forskning inom alla tre områdena och de är också är relevanta för många civila tillämpningar.

För det första problemet, visuell objektsföljning, innehåller avhandlingen tre bidrag som behandlar utvärdering av metoder för så kallad korttidsföljning, d.v.s. följning av enstaka objekt i korta sekvenser givet objektets initiala position och utbredning. Det första bidraget är ett dataset som bland annat använts i den första tävlingen i korttidsföljning i termisk infraröd video. Det andra bidraget är en metod för semi-automatisk annotering av multimodala videosekvenser. Slutligen föreslås också en metod för automatisk korttidsföljning av ett objekt i termisk infraröd video.

Det andra problemet, anomalidetektion, avser detektion av sällsynta objekt eller händelser, så kallade anomalier. Det första bidraget inom detta område är en metod för anomalidetektion där det inte finns några exempel på hur anomalierna ser ut. Metoden bygger på så kallade generativa adversiella nätverk, en form av neurala nätverk. Det andra bidraget är en metod för hinderdetektion framför tåg, ett tidigare obehandlat problem. Metoden uppdaterar kontinuerligt en modell av bakgrunden och detektioner av hinder definieras som missade detektioner av bakgrund. Det tredje och sista bidraget inom området anomalidetektion är en metod för karaktärisering och klassificering av automatiskt detekterade fjärrvärmeläckor med syfte att minimera antalet falsklarm.

Slutligen, så innehåller avhandlingen också ett bidrag inom området för övergång mellan två olika modaliteter. Övergången från termiskt infrarött till perceptuellt realistiska visuella bilder är också det ett tidigare obehandlat problem, relevant för till exempel säkerhetssystem i bilar. Metoden som föreslås använder sig av neurala nätverk och drar nytta av den skillnad i skärpa som finns hos det mänskliga ögat för skillnader i färg jämfört med skillnader i luminans.

ABSTRACT

Thermal cameras have historically been of interest mainly for military applications. Increasing image quality and resolution combined with decreasing camera price and size during recent years have, however, opened up new application areas. They are now widely used for civilian applications, e.g., within industry, to search for missing persons, in automotive safety, as well as for medical applications. Thermal cameras are useful as soon as there exists a measurable temperature difference. Compared to cameras operating in the visual spectrum, they are advantageous due to their ability to see in total darkness, robustness to illumination variations, and less intrusion on privacy.

This thesis addresses the problem of automatic image analysis in thermal infrared images with a focus on machine learning methods. The main purpose of this thesis is to study the variations of processing required due to the thermal infrared data modality. In particular, three different problems are addressed: visual object tracking, anomaly detection, and modality transfer. All these are research areas that have been and currently are subject to extensive research. Furthermore, they are all highly relevant for a number of different real-world applications.

The first addressed problem is *visual object tracking*, a problem for which no prior information other than the initial location of the object is given. The main contribution concerns benchmarking of short-term single-object (STSO) visual object tracking methods in thermal infrared images. The proposed dataset, LTIR (Linköping Thermal Infrared), was integrated in the VOT-TIR2015 challenge, introducing the first ever organized challenge on STSO tracking in thermal infrared video. Another contribution also related to benchmarking is a novel, recursive, method for semi-automatic annotation of multi-modal video sequences. Based on only a few initial annotations, a video object segmentation (VOS) method proposes segmentations for all remaining frames and difficult parts in need for additional manual annotation are automatically detected. The third contribution to the problem of visual object tracking is a template tracking method based on a non-parametric probability density model of the object’s thermal radiation using channel representations.

The second addressed problem is *anomaly detection*, i.e., detection of rare objects or events. The main contribution is a method for truly unsupervised anomaly detection based on Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs). The method employs joint training of the generator and an observation to latent space encoder, enabling stratification of the latent space and, thus, also separation of normal and anomalous samples. The second contribution is the previously unaddressed problem of obstacle detection in front of moving trains using a train-mounted thermal camera. Adaptive correlation filters are updated continuously and missed detections of background are treated as detections of anomalies, or obstacles. The third contribution to the problem of anomaly detection is a method for characterization and classification of automatically detected district heat leakages for the purpose of false alarm reduction.

Finally, the thesis addresses the problem of *modality transfer* between thermal infrared and visual spectrum images, a previously unaddressed problem. The contribution is a method based on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), enabling perceptually realistic transformations of thermal infrared to visual images. By careful design of the loss function the method becomes robust to image pair misalignments. The method exploits the lower acuity for color differences than for luminance possessed by the human visual system, separating the loss into a luminance and a chrominance part.

Acknowledgments

As my masters degree was approaching in 2013, I was thinking about what to do with my future. I had at that time spent many years within the educational system and felt a desire to try something different. I was not quite sure about precisely what I wanted to do, but I was completely certain that I did *not* want to enrol as a PhD student, and yet, here I am. The opportunity to combine industry and academia as an industrial PhD student was an offer I could not refuse, a decision I have (almost) never regretted.

There have been many emotions related to this journey. I have been determined to succeed, while at the same time scared to fail. I have been nervous prior to presentations, happy and proud of fellow PhD students, and grateful for being given this opportunity. At the same time, I have been angry at unfair reviews and confusing code, tired and fed-up with late nights, annoyed and irritated as deadlines have approached, relieved as they were over, dejected after rejects and hopeful after accepts. I have felt lost among code lines, while at the same time focused on the goal, divided between academia and industry, while at the same time strengthened by the combination. To be honest, I have not loved every part of the journey, but being a part of the academic society is a wonderful thing. I have met numerous inspiring, bright, persons of which I would like to mention a few in particular.

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Linköping, October 2019
Amanda Berg

About the cover

(Front) A mosaic of aerial thermal infrared images and a set of connected, artificial, neurons organized in the shape of a brain to symbolize artificial learning for the purpose of automatic image analysis.

(Back) Thermal radiation interpreted by a three-year old.

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PART I

BACKGROUND

INTRODUCTION

Automatic image analysis in thermal infrared images has historically been of interest mainly for military purposes. Increasing image quality and resolution combined with decreasing camera price and size during recent years have, however, opened up new application areas. Thermal cameras are advantageous in many applications due to their ability to see in total darkness, their robustness to illumination changes, and less intrusion on privacy. Thermal infrared images are visual displays of the measured thermal infrared radiation within an area and they can reveal additional information *beyond the visible spectrum*, a few examples are provided in Fig. 1.1.

This thesis addresses automatic analysis in thermal infrared images with a focus on machine learning methods. The main purpose is to study the variations of processing required due to the thermal infrared data modality. The thesis addresses three problems highly relevant for a number of different real-world applications: visual object tracking, anomaly detection, and modality transfer.

1.1 Motivation

The electromagnetic spectrum is broad and divided into smaller bands based on their different properties. Close to the visual part lies the *near infrared* wavelength band. Visual and near infrared cameras measure mostly *reflected* radiation. Radiation within the *thermal infrared* wavelength band have longer wavelength. In contrast to visual and near infrared cameras, thermal cameras measure mostly *emitted radiation*. The observed phenomena related to reflected and emitted radiation differ in several aspects, indicating that image analysis in thermal infrared images is slightly different than that of visual images.

There are two common misconceptions regarding image analysis in thermal infrared images. The first misconception is related to the temperature

Figure 1.1: Thermal infrared images can provide additional information beyond what can be seen in the visible spectrum. (a) Someone has been walking on the floor, (b) someone has touched the plant, (c) a thermal infrared image reveals which bricks have been touched recently.

of interesting objects in the scene. It is often assumed to be significantly different than the temperature of the background, requiring only a straightforward threshold in order to separate an interesting object from background. This assumption is valid in some special cases, but for most applications the situation is more complex, some examples are provided in Fig. 1.2. Object temperatures may vary over the object and some parts may be of the same temperature as the background. The second misconception is that thermal infrared image analysis is identical to image analysis of grayscale visual images. Hence, image analysis methods suitable for visual images would also be suitable for thermal infrared images. There are, however, significant differences between the two types of imagery. For example, in the noise characteristics, the amount of discernible spatial patterns, the data format, and how the emitted radiation behave in comparison to reflected radiation.

Machine learning, as a part of the broader field of artificial intelligence, is an area of intense research. A machine learning method is an algorithm that is able to learn from data. As one of the keys to understanding intelligence itself, learning methods provide a highly effective approach to solving problems too complex for hand-crafted programs designed by humans. Machine learning methods can solve many different types of tasks. In this thesis, they are applied to the problems of: visual object tracking, anomaly detection, and modality transfer.

Many applications connected to thermal cameras can be related to a sustainable society, for example, prevention and localisation of energy losses, as

Figure 1.2: A few examples of situations where thresholding based on temperature in order to separate an interesting object from the background will not work.

well as environmental friendly transportation. Two of the included publications address these areas. Paper E addresses reduction of false alarms among automatically detected district heating leakages. Detection is performed in thermographic images captured with an airborne thermal camera. In addition, a method for temporal analysis of energy losses of a district heating network given two or more acquisitions of thermal imagery is presented. In Paper D, an automatic method for rail and obstacle detection using a train-mounted thermal camera is proposed. The system aims at providing an early warning to train drivers under impaired view. An early warning enables the driver to break before collision, significantly reducing repair costs.

1.2 Goals of this thesis

The aim of the work leading to this thesis has been to study the variations of processing required due to the thermal infrared data modality. The topic is broad, and an investigation of all possible aspects is out of scope for this thesis. The goal has, therefore, been to approach the subject from a few different directions, more specifically, the problems of visual object tracking, anomaly detection, and modality transfer, or the methodology of benchmarking, method design, and real-world applications. Not all of the proposed methods are limited to thermal infrared images. The idea behind each one of the included publications has, however, stemmed from a problem or an application related to the thermal infrared modality. The problem formulations of each one of the included publications are quite narrow, but they are all part of the overall aim of the thesis.

Paper A, B, and C address the problem of visual object tracking. Paper A and B address benchmarking of short-term tracking methods in thermal infrared images. Paper B proposes a multi-modal semi-automatic annotation method that is not limited to thermal infrared images, but the idea arose from the desire to create a multi-modal dataset for the VOT-RGBT 2019 challenge

[106]. Paper C proposes a template-based tracking method. The employed representation is particularly beneficial for the thermal infrared modality.

Paper D, E, and F address the problem of anomaly detection. The proposed approach in Paper D, adaptive correlation filters, is suitable for thermal infrared images since there are no shadows or rapid illumination changes present. The proposed method in Paper E for false alarm reduction is applied, but not limited to, thermal infrared images. Paper F proposes a method for unsupervised anomaly detection. The idea arose from the desire to perform unsupervised anomaly detection in thermal infrared images, but due to the lack of available annotated datasets, the evaluation was performed on grayscale visual images. The method is not limited to any specific modality.

Finally, Paper G addresses the problem of modality transfer between thermal infrared and perceptually realistic visual RGB images. The problems that arise due to the thermal modality are addressed and the proposed method is designed based on these. For example, since it is very difficult to obtain perfect pixel to pixel correspondence between a thermal infrared and visual RGB image due to the physical properties of the different materials of the lenses, the method had to be robust to image pair misalignment.

1.3 Contributions

This thesis contains contributions within the field of image analysis in thermal infrared images. The included publications address the problems of visual object tracking (Paper A, B, and C), anomaly detection (Paper D, E, and F), and modality transfer (Paper G). The common feature of Paper C-G is that they all apply learning methods to the different problems to various degrees.

Common performance metrics and datasets are necessary for comparison of tracking results between different tracking methods. Without the existence of a common dataset that is sufficiently challenging, publications presenting new tracking methods tend to use proprietary datasets for evaluation. Consequently making it difficult to get an overview of the current status and advances within the field. Paper A argued that existing datasets at that time for benchmarking of tracking methods in thermal infrared video had become outdated. A new, publicly available, more challenging, **thermal infrared benchmark** for short-term single-object tracking methods was presented. The proposed dataset LTIR (Linköping Thermal Infrared) was integrated in the VOT2015 challenge, introducing the VOT-TIR2015 challenge [62] as the first ever organized challenge on short-term single-object tracking in thermal infrared images. LTIR was also used in a revised form in the VOT-TIR2016 challenge [65].

Apart from images, a tracking benchmark also requires ground-truth annotations. Manual ground-truth annotation of video sequences is a labour-intensive process, inevitable in many computer vision applications. In Pa-

per B, a novel, recursive, **semi-automatic annotation method** was proposed. Based on only a few initial manual annotations, a video object segmentation (VOS) method proposes segmentations for all remaining frames in a multi-modal video sequence. Difficult parts that require additional manual annotations are automatically detected. The proposed method was estimated to reduce the workload for a human annotator with about 78% compared to full manual annotation. Sequences annotated with the proposed method was used in the VOT-RGBT 2019 tracking challenge [106].

Paper C addresses the problem of short-term, single-object tracking for the case of thermal infrared video. The publication introduces a **template-based tracking method** (ABCD) designed specifically for thermal infrared, with an online template update. Template-based tracking methods for visual video was seeing fast progress at that time, while not being previously explored for thermal infrared video. The proposed method was not restricted by some of the usual constraints for thermal infrared tracking methods, e.g., warm objects, low spatial resolution, and static camera. When participating in the VOT-TIR2015 tracking challenge [62], ABCD ended up in sixth place out of 24 competing trackers.

Detection of previously unseen rare objects or events, so called anomalies, in high dimensional data such as images is a challenging problem. Three of the included publications address this problem. Paper D proposes a **method for obstacle detection in front of moving trains** based on adaptive correlation filters. TIR images were captured from a camera mounted in the front end of a train. Despite its similarity to road and lane detection, the problem was previously unaddressed.

Paper E applies learning methods to the problem of false alarm reduction among automatically detected district heating leakages. Pixel intensity values of district heating leakages are treated as anomalies compared to the distribution of normal intensity values. A method for **characterization and classification of automatically detected district heat leakages for false alarm reduction** is proposed. In addition, a method for temporal analysis of the status of a district heating network in the case of multiple acquisitions is also presented.

In Paper F, it is noted that previously published anomaly detection methods based on Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) often claim to be unsupervised while using anomaly free, i.e., weakly labelled, data for training. In the paper, performance of several state-of-the-art methods is evaluated on contaminated data. An additional encoder network, trained jointly with the generator is proposed. The joint training leads to a separation in latent space between normal and anomalous samples. The proposed method for **unsupervised adversarial learning of anomaly detection** achieved state-of-the-art performance.

Machine learning methods typically require large amounts of labelled data. Large datasets and/or networks pre-trained on thermal infrared images are

rare and cross-spectral transfer learning from visual RGB to thermal infrared is, therefore, highly relevant. There are two main approaches for knowledge transfer from a model pre-trained on visual images to thermal infrared images. First, the model itself can be adapted using, e.g., transfer learning techniques that modify the coefficients of trained parameters. Another alternative is to find a mapping between the two modalities. The first ever published method on **perceptually realistic thermal infrared to visual spectrum image transformation** is presented in Paper G. Two fully automatic versions of the same approach based on Convolutional Neural Networks robust to image pair misalignments are proposed.

In summary, the contributions of this thesis concern applications of automatic image analysis methods onto thermal infrared images. The methods proposed in Paper B and F are, however, not limited to thermal infrared and can be applied to any image modality. The proposed benchmark (Paper A) raised the standard for publicly available thermal infrared tracking datasets and increased the visibility for thermal infrared tracking through its role in the VOT-TIR 2015 challenge. The included publications have concerned previously unaddressed problems (Paper D and G), have achieved state-of-the-art performance (Paper F), and have adapted methods common for visual images to thermal infrared (Paper C, D, and E).

1.4 Outline

This thesis is organized into two main parts. Part I provides background theory for the publications included in Part II. Parts of the material presented in Part I has already been published by the author in technical reports and conference articles. There are also parts that appeared in the author's licentiate thesis [25].

1.4.1 Outline Part I: Background

Chapter 2 gives an overview of the physical principles related to thermal infrared imaging as well as explains its advantages and limitations. It also presents the main differences between image analysis in visual and thermal images. The contents of Chapter 2 are relevant for most of the included papers in this thesis.

Chapters 3 and 4 describe the background theory for Paper C, D, E, F, and G related to representation and learning methods. In the subsequent chapter, Chapter 5, the three addressed problems: visual object tracking, anomaly detection, and modality transfer are introduced. The chapter also describes their relevance to real-world applications. Finally, concluding remarks and future work are given in Chapter 6.

1.4.2 Outline Part II: Included Publications

Preprint versions of seven publications are included in Part II. The abstracts together with a description of the background and author's contributions are summarized in the next section.

1.5 Included publications

Paper A: “A Thermal Object Tracking Benchmark”

A. Berg, J. Ahlberg, and M. Felsberg. “A Thermal Object Tracking Benchmark”. In: *2015 12th IEEE International Conference on Advanced Video and Signal Based Surveillance (AVSS)*. Aug. 2015, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/AVSS.2015.7301772

Abstract: Short-term single-object (STSO) tracking in thermal images is a challenging problem relevant in a growing number of applications. In order to evaluate STSO tracking algorithms on visual imagery, there are de facto standard benchmarks. However, we argue that tracking in thermal imagery is different than in visual imagery, and that a separate benchmark is needed. The available thermal infrared datasets are few and the existing ones are not challenging for modern tracking algorithms. Therefore, we hereby propose a thermal infrared benchmark according to the Visual Object Tracking (VOT) protocol for evaluation of STSO tracking methods. The benchmark includes the new LTIR dataset containing 20 thermal image sequences which have been collected from multiple sources and annotated in the format used in the VOT Challenge. In addition, we show that the ranking of different tracking principles differ between the visual and thermal benchmarks, confirming the need for the new benchmark.

Background and author’s contributions: This publication describes a new thermal infrared dataset (LTIR) for evaluation of short term, single object (STSO) trackers. Compared to previously available datasets, the LTIR dataset contained both 8- and 16-bit data, had higher resolution, more challenging sequences, as well as sequences captured with both moving and stationary sensors. The LTIR dataset was also used in the first thermal infrared tracking challenge for STSO trackers, VOT-TIR2015 [62]. The author was part of developing the ideas for this publication, did the data collection and annotations, conducted experiments, and did the main part of the writing.

Paper B: “Semi-automatic Annotation of Objects in Visual-Thermal Video”

A. Berg, J. Johnander, F. Durand De Gevigney, J. Ahlberg, and M. Felsberg. “Semi-automatic Annotation of Objects in Visual-Thermal Video”. In: *IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision Workshops (ICCVW)*. Oct. 2019

Abstract: Deep learning requires large amounts of annotated data. Manual annotation of objects in video is, regardless of annotation type, a tedious and time-consuming process. In particular, for scarcely used image modalities human annotation is hard to justify. In such cases, semi-automatic annotation provides an acceptable option.

In this work, a recursive, semi-automatic annotation method for video is presented. The proposed method utilizes a state-of-the-art video object segmentation method to propose initial annotations for all frames in a video based on only a few manual object segmentations. In the case of a multi-modal dataset, the multi-modality is exploited to refine the proposed annotations even further. The final tentative annotations are presented to the user for manual correction.

The method is evaluated on a subset of the RGBT-234 visual-thermal dataset reducing the workload for a human annotator with approximately 78% compared to full manual annotation. Utilizing the proposed pipeline, sequences are annotated for the VOT-RGBT 2019 challenge.

Background and author’s contributions: In this publication, a novel, semi-automatic annotation method for, but not limited to, multi-modal video was proposed. The method was used to generate rotated bounding boxes for the VOT-RGBT 2019 tracking challenge [106]. Compared to previous semi-automatic methods, the failure detection is automatic and the method recursively recommends where additional manual annotations are needed. The author was part of developing the ideas for this publication, implemented the failure detection and segmentation fusion, and did the main part of the writing. Experiments were conducted by the author in collaboration with Joakim Johnander and Flavie Durand De Gevigney.

Paper C: “Channel Coded Distribution Field Tracking for Thermal Infrared Imagery”

A. Berg, J. Ahlberg, and M. Felsberg. “Channel Coded Distribution Field Tracking for Thermal Infrared Imagery”. In: *2016 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops (CVPRW)*. June 2016, pp. 1248–1256. DOI: 10.1109/CVPRW.2016.158

Abstract: We address *short-term, single-object tracking*, a topic that is currently seeing fast progress for visual video, for the case of *thermal infrared (TIR) imagery*. The fast progress has been possible thanks to the development of new template-based tracking methods with online template updates, methods which have not been explored for TIR tracking. Instead, tracking methods used for TIR are often subject to a number of constraints, e.g., warm objects, low spatial resolution, and static camera. As TIR cameras become less noisy and get higher resolution these constraints are less relevant, and for emerging civilian applications, e.g., surveillance and automotive safety, new tracking methods are needed.

Due to the special characteristics of TIR imagery, we argue that template-based trackers based on *distribution fields* should have an advantage over trackers based on spatial structure features. In this paper, we propose a template-based tracking method (ABCD) designed specifically for TIR and not being restricted by any of the constraints above. In order to avoid background contamination of the object template, we propose to exploit background information for the online template update and to adaptively select the object region used for tracking. Moreover, we propose a novel method for estimating object scale change. The proposed tracker is evaluated on the VOT-TIR2015 and VOT2015 datasets using the VOT evaluation toolkit and a comparison of relative ranking of all common participating trackers in the challenges is provided. Further, the proposed tracker, ABCD, and the VOT-TIR2015 winner SRDCFir are evaluated on maritime data. Experimental results show that the ABCD tracker performs particularly well on thermal infrared sequences.

Background and author’s contributions: In this publication, a template-based tracking method designed for thermal infrared images is presented. The method extends the EDFT [60] tracker to adaptively select the object region for tracking and to incorporate background information in the model update. The author developed the ideas for this publication, implemented the proposed method, conducted the experiments and evaluation, and did the main part of the writing.

Paper D: “Detecting Rails and Obstacles Using a Train-Mounted Thermal Camera”

A. Berg, K. Öfjäll, J. Ahlberg, and M. Felsberg. “Detecting Rails and Obstacles Using a Train-Mounted Thermal Camera”. In: *Scandinavian Conference on Image Analysis (SCIA)*. Springer International Publishing, 2015, pp. 492–503. ISBN: 978-3-319-19665-7. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-19665-7_42

Abstract: We propose a method for detecting obstacles on the railway in front of a moving train using a monocular thermal camera. The problem is motivated by the large number of collisions between trains and various obstacles, resulting in reduced safety and high costs. The proposed method includes a novel way of detecting the rails in the imagery, as well as a way to detect anomalies on the railway. While the problem at a first glance looks similar to road and lane detection, which in the past has been a popular research topic, a closer look reveals that the problem at hand is previously unaddressed. As a consequence, relevant datasets are missing as well, and thus our contribution is two-fold: We propose an approach to the novel problem of obstacle detection on railways and we describe the acquisition of a novel data set.

Background and author’s contributions: This publication describes new methods for rail detection and correction in thermal infrared images as well as detection of obstacles on the railway. The author was part of developing the ideas for this publication, implemented the anomaly detector and rail corrector, conducted experiments on the same, wrote Section 3 and 4 and was the main author.

Paper E: “Enhanced Analysis of Thermographic Images for Monitoring of District Heat Pipe Networks”

A. Berg, J. Ahlberg, and M. Felsberg. “Enhanced Analysis of Thermographic Images for Monitoring of District Heat Pipe Networks”. In: *Pattern Recognition Letters* 83 (2016). Advances in Pattern Recognition in Remote Sensing, pp. 215–223. ISSN: 0167-8655. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patrec.2016.07.002>

Abstract: We address two problems related to large-scale aerial monitoring of district heating networks. First, we propose a classification scheme to reduce the number of false alarms among automatically detected leakages in district heating networks. The leakages are detected in images captured by an airborne thermal camera, and each detection corresponds to an image region with abnormally high temperature. This approach yields a significant number of false positives, and we propose to reduce this number in two steps; by (a) using a building segmentation scheme in order to remove detections on buildings, and (b) to use a machine learning approach to classify the remaining detections as true or false leakages. We provide extensive experimental analysis on real-world data, showing that this post-processing step significantly improves the usefulness of the system. Second, we propose a method for characterization of leakages over time, i.e., repeating the image acquisition one or a few years later and indicate areas that suffer from an increased energy loss. We address the problem of finding trends in the degradation of pipe networks in order to plan for long-term maintenance, and propose a visualization scheme exploiting the consecutive data collections.

Background and author’s contributions: In this journal article, methods for large-scale monitoring of district heating networks are described. The article focuses on the reduction of false alarms among automatically detected areas with abnormally high temperatures. In addition, a method and visualization technique for temporal analysis given several acquisitions of the same area are proposed. The author was part of developing the ideas for this publication, did the data collection and annotations, implemented the proposed method, conducted the experiments and evaluation, and did the main part of the writing.

Paper F: “Unsupervised Adversarial Learning of Anomaly Detection in the Wild”

A. Berg, J. Ahlberg, and M. Felsberg. “Unsupervised Adversarial Learning of Anomaly Detection in the Wild”. In: *Submitted to the 24th European Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ECAI 2020)*. 2019

Abstract: Unsupervised learning of anomaly detection in high-dimensional data, such as images, is a challenging problem recently subject to intense research. Through careful modelling of the data distribution of normal samples, it is possible to detect deviant samples, so called anomalies. Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) can model the highly complex, high-dimensional data distribution of normal image samples, and have shown to be a suitable approach to the problem. Previously published GAN-based anomaly detection methods often assume that anomaly-free data is available for training. However, this assumption is not valid in most real-life scenarios, a.k.a. in the wild. In this work, we evaluate the effects of anomaly contaminations in the training data on state-of-the-art GAN-based anomaly detection methods. As expected, detection performance deteriorates. To address this performance drop, we propose to add an additional encoder network already at training time and show that joint generator-encoder training stratifies the latent space, mitigating the problem with contaminated data. We show experimentally that the norm of a query image in this stratified latent space becomes a highly significant cue to discriminate anomalies from normal data. The proposed method achieves state-of-the-art performance on CIFAR-10 as well as on a large, previously untested dataset with cell images.

Background and author’s contributions: This paper employs a Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) for the purpose of anomaly detection. In contrast to previous GAN-based anomaly detection methods, an encoder is trained together with the generator and the latent space of the trained encoder is examined. It is concluded that the technique used for encoder training affects the structure of the latent space. Further, the norm of latent vectors can serve as an important cue when discriminating normal samples from anomalous. The author developed the ideas for this publication, implemented the proposed method, conducted the experiments and the evaluation, and did the main part of the writing.

Paper G: “Generating Visible Spectrum Images from Thermal Infrared”

A. Berg, J. Ahlberg, and M. Felsberg. “Generating Visible Spectrum Images from Thermal Infrared”. In: *2018 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops (CVPRW)*. June 2018. DOI: 10.1109/CVPRW.2018.00159

Abstract: Transformation of thermal infrared (TIR) images into visual, i.e. perceptually realistic color (RGB) images, is a challenging problem. TIR cameras have the ability to see in scenarios where vision is severely impaired, for example in total darkness or fog, and they are commonly used, e.g., for surveillance and automotive applications. However, interpretation of TIR images is difficult, especially for untrained operators. Enhancing the TIR image display by transforming it into a plausible, visual, perceptually realistic RGB image presumably facilitates interpretation. Existing grayscale to RGB, so called, colorization methods cannot be applied to TIR images directly since those methods only estimate the chrominance and not the luminance.

In the absence of conventional colorization methods, we propose two fully automatic TIR to visual color image transformation methods, a two-step and an integrated approach, based on Convolutional Neural Networks. The methods require neither pre- nor postprocessing, do not require any user input, and are robust to image pair misalignments. We show that the methods do indeed produce perceptually realistic results on publicly available data, which is assessed both qualitatively and quantitatively.

Background and author’s contributions: This publication proposes an approach for automatic transformation from thermal infrared to perceptually realistic color (RGB) images, a previously unaddressed problem. The proposed approach was based on an autoencoder architecture due to the ability of Convolutional Neural Networks to model semantic representations. The author developed the ideas for this publication, implemented the proposed method, conducted the experiments and evaluation, and did the main part of the writing.

1.6 Additional publications

Parts of the material presented in this thesis also appeared in the author's licentiate thesis:

A. Berg. *Detection and Tracking in Thermal Infrared Imagery*. Licentiate thesis No. 1744. Linköping University Electronic Press, 2016. ISBN: 978-91-7685-789-2. DOI: 10.3384/lic.diva-126955

1.6.1 Preliminary versions of included publications

Paper E is a journal extension of the following three publications. The first one [18] is an early version that was rewritten to form [14]. In [13], a temporal analysis of the district heating pipes was added. This extension together with the classification in [14] was rewritten and extended in Paper E.

A. Berg, J. Ahlberg, and M. Felsberg. “Classifying District Heating Network Leakages in Aerial Thermal Imagery”. In: *Swedish Symposium on Image Analysis (SSBA)*. 2014
(Also [18])

A. Berg and J. Ahlberg. “Classification of Leakage Detections Acquired by Airborne Thermography of District Heating Networks”. In: *Pattern Recognition in Remote Sensing (PRRS), IAPR Workshop on*. 2014. DOI: 10.1109/PRRS.2014.6914288
(Also [14])

A. Berg and J. Ahlberg. “Classification and Temporal Analysis of District Heating Leakages in Thermal Images”. In: *The 14th International Symposium on District Heating and Cooling (DHC)*. 2014
(Also [13])

The publication below, describing the LTIR dataset, is an early version of Paper A. The manuscript was rewritten for Paper A and extended with a benchmark based on the VOT-protocol. Results from seven state-of-the-art visual object tracking methods was reported.

A. Berg, J. Ahlberg, and M. Felsberg. “A Thermal Infrared Dataset for Evaluation of Short-term Tracking Methods”. In: *Swedish Symposium on Image Analysis (SSBA)*. 2015

1.6.2 Publications related to included papers

A. Berg, J. Ahlberg, and M. Felsberg. “Object Tracking in Thermal Infrared Imagery based on Channel Coded Distribution Fields”. In: *Swedish Symposium on Image Analysis (SSBA)*. 2017 (Revised version of Paper C.)

A. Berg, J. Ahlberg, and M. Felsberg. “Visual Spectrum Image Generation from Thermal Infrared”. In: *Swedish Symposium on Image Analysis (SSBA)*. 2019 (Revised version of Paper G.)

1.6.3 Other publications

J. Ahlberg and A. Berg. “Evaluating Template Rescaling in Short-term Single-object Tracking”. In: *IEEE International Conference on Advanced Video- and Signal-based Surveillance Workshops*. Aug. 2015, pp. 1–4. DOI: 10.1109/AVSS.2015.7301745

M. Felsberg, A. Berg, G. Häger, J. Ahlberg, M. Kristan, J. Matas, A. Leonardis, L. Cehovin, G. Fernandez, et al. “The Thermal Infrared Visual Object Tracking VOT-TIR2015 Challenge Results”. In: *IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision Workshops (ICCVW)*. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE), 2015, pp. 639–651. DOI: 10.1109/ICCVW.2015.86

A. Berg, M. Felsberg, G. Häger, and J. Ahlberg. “An Overview of the Thermal Infrared Visual Object Tracking VOT-TIR2015 Challenge”. In: *Swedish Symposium on Image Analysis (SSBA)*. 2016 (Overview of the previous paper.)

M. Felsberg, M. Kristan, J. Matas, A. Leonardis, R. Pflugfelder, G. Häger, A. Berg, A. Eldesokey, J. Ahlberg, et al. “The Thermal Infrared Visual Object Tracking VOT-TIR2016 Challenge Results”. In: *Proceedings on the European Conference on Computer Vision Workshops (ECCVW)*. vol. 9914. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Springer, Cham, 2016, pp. 824–849. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-48881-3_55

M. Kristan, J. Matas, A. Leonardis, M. Felsberg, R. Pflugfelder, J.-K. Kamarainen, L. Cehovin, O. Drbohlav, A. Lukezic, A.

Berg, A. Eldesokey, et al. “The Seventh Visual Object Tracking VOT2019 Challenge Results”. In: *2019 IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision Workshops (ICCVW)*. 2019

T. Nawaz, A. Berg, J. Ferryman, J. Ahlberg, and M. Felsberg. “Effective Evaluation of Privacy Protection Techniques in Visible and Thermal Imagery”. In: *Journal of Electronic Imaging (JEI)* 26.5 (2017), pp. 1–16. DOI: 10.1117/1.JEI.26.5.051408

J. Heggenes, A. Odland, T. Chevalier, J. Ahlberg, A. Berg, and D. Bjerketvedt. “Herbivore Grazing—or Trampling? Trampling Effects by a Large Ungulate in Cold High-latitude Ecosystems”. In: *Ecology and Evolution* 7.16 (2017), pp. 6423–6431. DOI: 10.1002/ece3.3130

THERMAL INFRARED IMAGING

Thermal infrared radiation is emitted, reflected, and transmitted around us every day. While rarely considered on a daily basis, the temperature difference of different objects can provide valuable information. Visual displays of the measured thermal infrared radiation, thermal infrared images, form the basis of this thesis. The following chapter gives a brief overview of the underlying physics as well as automatic image analysis in thermal infrared images. The chapter also explains the relation between infrared light and the planet Uranus, shows examples of the properties of different materials in thermal infrared, and explains why it is not possible to see through windows with thermal cameras. This chapter is a revised version of Chapter 2 in the author's licentiate thesis [25].

2.1 Infrared and thermal radiation

The discovery of infrared radiation is credited to the astronomer and composer William Herschel (1738-1822). In the year 1800, he conducted a series of experiments [87, 88, 89] where he postulated and tried to prove that visible light and radiant heat was of the same quantity. The postulation was based on one of his first experiments [87], where he used a prism to split sunlight into different colors and then measured the radiant heat of each color. To his surprise, his control thermometer placed outside the visible sunlight was heated as well. Finally, the following conclusion was made:

“To conclude, if we call light, those rays which illuminate objects, and radiant heat, those which heat bodies, it may be inquired, whether light be essentially different from radiant heat? In answer to which I would suggest, that we are not allowed, by the rules of philosophizing, to admit two different causes to explain certain effects, if they may be accounted for by one.”[87]

Figure 2.1: Infrared radiation is a part of the electromagnetic spectrum. Long-wave, and sometimes midwave, infrared is commonly referred to as thermal infrared. Between 5–8 μm , the atmosphere attenuates most of the radiation.

Apart from these experiments, William Herschel is famous for writing 24 symphonies and, together with his sister Caroline, building telescopes and discovering four moons, eight comets, and one planet (Uranus) [166]. William Herschel draw these conclusions without neither the knowledge of electromagnetic radiation, nor the concept of wavelength. It is now known that the visible and infrared wavelength bands only span a small part of the electromagnetic spectrum, as illustrated in Fig. 2.1. The name, *infrared*, originates from the Latin word *infra*, which means *below*. That is, the infrared band lies below the visual red light band, since it has lower frequency.

The infrared wavelength band is in turn usually divided into smaller parts based on their different properties. The near infrared (NIR, wavelengths 0.7–1 μm) and shortwave infrared (SWIR, 1–3 μm) bands are dominated by *reflected* radiation and are dependent on illumination. Essentially, they behave similarly to visual light, except that we cannot see it. In contrast, the midwave infrared (MWIR, 3–5 μm), longwave infrared (LWIR, 8–12 μm), and far infrared (FIR, 12–1000 μm) bands are dominated by *emitted* radiation. Other definitions of the infrared bands exist as well. LWIR, and sometimes MWIR, is commonly referred to as thermal infrared (TIR).

All objects with temperatures above absolute zero *emit* thermal radiation to a different extent depending on temperature and material. Emitted thermal radiation originates from the conversion of an object’s thermal energy into electromagnetic energy. Objects at normal everyday temperatures emit mostly in the LWIR band, while a hot object like the sun emits most in the visual band, thus making the LWIR band the most suitable for night vision.

When interacting with matter, electromagnetic radiation is absorbed (α), transmitted (τ) and/or reflected (ρ). The total radiation law states that $1 = \alpha + \rho + \tau$ where $\alpha, \tau, \rho \in [0, 1]$. An object defined as a black body is an opaque and non-reflective object that absorbs all incident radiation ($\alpha = 1$). Black bodies do not exist in nature, but are commonly used as an approximation.

Figure 2.2: Atmospheric attenuation depends on radiation wavelength. Image courtesy of Jörgen Ahlberg.

Examples of black body radiation curves for some known objects can be seen in Fig. 2.3. Note that the peak of the sun lies in the reflective part of the electromagnetic spectrum. The blackbody radiation curves were described by Max Planck almost exactly 100 years after Herschel’s discovery of infrared radiation [158].

Emissivity (ϵ) is the ratio of the actual emittance of an object to the emittance of a black body at the same temperature. Further, Kirchhoff’s law states that $\alpha = \epsilon$, i.e., $\epsilon = 1$ for a black body. Since emissivity is material dependent, it is an important property when measuring temperatures with a thermal camera. An example of how the emissivity of an object can affect what is perceived is given in Fig. 2.4.

Due to scattering by particles and absorption by gases, the atmosphere will attenuate radiation, making the measured apparent temperature decrease with increased distance. The level of attenuation depends on radiation wavelength, Fig. 2.2. As can be seen in the figure, there are some sections in which the atmosphere transmits a major part of the radiation. These are called the atmospheric windows; there is one VNIR (Visual and NIR) window, two windows in SWIR, two windows in MWIR, and a large window in LWIR [165].

This section only provides a brief overview of the topic, for more information on thermal infrared detectors and physical principles, see for example [165, 166].

2.2 Thermal imaging

Thermal images are visual displays of the measured thermal radiation within an area. Again, it should be emphasized that thermal cameras are sensitive to *emitted* radiation in everyday temperatures and that they should not be confused with NIR and SWIR cameras that mostly measure the *reflected* radiation. They are dependent on illumination and behave in general in a similar way as visual cameras.

Figure 2.3: Black body radiation for different objects. As the temperature increases, the peak of the emitted radiation moves towards shorter wavelengths and higher intensities. The dashed lines mark the visual part of the electromagnetic spectrum.

Figure 2.4: An example of how the emissivity of materials affects what is perceived. A transparent tape of another logo than that of the soda has been placed on the metal can. The can was then filled with hot water. The tape has higher emissivity than the can and appears warmer when measuring. Image courtesy of Jörgen Ahlberg and Patrik Stensbo.

Figure 2.5: The radiation measured by a thermal camera when observing an object is a combination of multiple sources, not only the amount of radiation emitted by the object, which is typically what is desired.

Thermal cameras are either cooled or uncooled. High-end cooled cameras can deliver hundreds of High Definition (HD) resolution frames per second and have a temperature sensitivity of 20 mK. Images are typically stored as 16 bits per pixel to allow a large dynamic range, for example 0–382.2K with a precision of 10 mK. Uncooled cameras usually have bolometer detectors and operate in LWIR. They yield noisier images at a lower framerate, but are smaller, silent, and less expensive.

A thermal camera is said to be *thermographic* if it is calibrated in order to measure temperatures. Some uncooled cameras provide access to the raw 16-bit intensity values, so called *radiometric* cameras, while others convert the images to 8-bits and compress them, e.g., using MPEG. In the latter case, the dynamic range is adaptively changed in order provide an image that looks good to the eye, but the temperature information is lost. For automatic analysis, such as target detection, classification, and tracking, it is in most cases preferable to use the original signal, i.e., the raw 16-bit intensity values from a radiometric camera.

In order to produce accurate thermographic measurements, all different sources of thermal radiation need to be considered, an illustration is provided in Fig. 2.5. The amount of radiation emitted by the object depends on its emissivity as explained in the previous section. In addition, thermal radiation from other objects are reflected on the surface of the object. Therefore, it is also important to know the reflectivity of the object. The amount of radiation that reaches the detector is affected by the atmosphere. Some is transmitted through the atmosphere, some is absorbed by the atmosphere, and some is even emitted from the atmosphere itself, in contrast to the visual band. Moreover, the camera itself emits thermal radiation during operation. In order to measure thermal radiation and, thus, temperatures as accurately as possible, all these effects need to be considered. At short distances, atmospheric effects can be disregarded. But for greater distances, e.g., from aircrafts as in Paper E, it is crucial to consider atmospheric effects if temperatures are to be measured correctly. However, if you are only interested in an image that looks good to the eye and not temperatures, these effects do not have to be taken

Figure 2.6: A thermal infrared image visualized using different color maps.

into account. In that case, thermal images can be used as visual displays of received thermal radiation on a sensor. When presented to an operator, color maps are often used to map pixel intensity values in order to visualize details more clearly. Examples of a thermal image with three widely used color maps can be seen in Fig. 2.6.

2.3 Advantages and limitations of thermal imaging

From the aspect of measuring temperatures, thermal imaging is not considered to be as accurate as contact methods. It is, however, advantageous compared to point-based methods when it comes to measuring the temperature distribution over a large area. In addition, thermal imaging, as well as pyrometry in general, provides the possibility of remote temperature measurement, which can be favourable in some applications.

Compared to visual cameras, thermal cameras are favourable as soon as there is a temperature difference connected to the object or phenomenon you want to detect. For example, emerging fires, humans, animals, increased body temperatures, or differences in heat transfer ability in materials. When it comes to applications, thermal cameras are especially advantageous to visual cameras in outdoor applications. Thermal cameras can produce an image with no or few distortions during darkness and/or difficult weather conditions (e.g. fog/rain/snow). This is again due to the fact that a thermal camera is sensitive for emitted radiation, even from relatively cold objects, in contrast to a visual or NIR camera that measures reflected radiation and thus depends on illumination.

Thermal cameras are expensive and have low resolution compared to visual cameras. State of the art is currently 1280x1024 pixels, and increased resolution comes with a higher price tag, up to €200 000. Prices depend on the choice of detector (cooled/uncooled, MWIR/LWIR), optics etc.

In comparison to a visual camera, a thermal camera typically requires more training for correct usage. In order to provide accurate measurements, the operator needs to be aware of the physical principles and phenomena com-

(a) Glass

(b) Water

(c) Plastic bag

Figure 2.7: Examples of a few different materials in RGB images (first row) versus thermal infrared images (second row).

monly viewed in thermal imagery. That is, the emissivity and reflectivity of different materials as well as the impact of the atmosphere and other objects.

From thermal images, it is not considered possible to perform person identification, a fact that is both an advantage as well as a limitation. Consequently, a thermal camera can be used in applications where preservation of privacy is crucial. If person identification is requested, the thermal camera has to be combined with a visual camera.

2.4 Image analysis in thermal infrared images

In this section, differences between thermal and visual images when performing automatic image analysis are described. Some descriptions are intentionally left brief since they are further described in Section 5.1 in relation to visual object tracking in thermal infrared.

Materials have different properties in the thermal and visual spectrum respectively, a few examples are provided in Fig. 2.7. Some materials that are reflective and/or transparent in the visual spectrum are not in the thermal spectrum and vice versa. For example, water and glass are opaque and highly reflective in the thermal spectrum while mostly transparent in the visual spectrum. Therefore, the lens of a thermal camera is not manufactured in glass but in another material, typically germanium, a material that is opaque and reflective in the visual spectrum but transparent in the thermal spectrum, see example in Fig. 2.9. Glass, water puddles and wet soil can cause reflections similar to shadows.

Figure 2.8: Four pieces of jersey fabric that have different visual color patterns. In the (a) visual spectrum, they are easily separated, while having identical appearance in the (b) thermal infrared spectrum.

Figure 2.9: Example of a germanium lens. Germanium is opaque and reflective in the visual spectrum while transparent in the thermal spectrum.

In the thermal infrared spectrum, there are no shadows since mostly emitted radiation is measured. In most applications, the emitted radiation changes much slower than the reflected radiation. That is, an object moving from a dark room into the sunlight will not immediately change its appearance (as it would in visual imagery).

Regarding noise, thermal imagery has different characteristics than visual imagery. Compared to a visual camera, a thermal infrared camera typically has more blooming, lower resolution and a larger percentage of dead pixels. Visual color patterns are discernible in thermal infrared images only if they correspond to variations in material or temperature, as illustrated in Fig. 2.8.

Finally, a thermal infrared camera is itself a source of thermal radiation. During operation, especially during start-up, it heats itself. The radiation reaching the sensor can to a large part originate from the camera itself. To compensate for this, thermal infrared cameras typically have internal thermometers and they also perform radiometric calibration at regular time intervals. During calibration, a plate with known temperature is inserted in front of the sensor, and frames are lost.

REPRESENTATION

As visible light enters our eyes through the cornea and spreads across the retina, the light intensity measured by the photosensitive cells is mapped to a different representation prior to interpretation [194]. Similarly, the grid of intensity values measured by a visual or thermal camera must, in computer vision, be mapped to a *representation* suitable for the problem at hand. The aim of a representation method is to extract the information relevant to the solution of the addressed problem in order to facilitate data processing [104]. The following chapter introduces representation methods and, in particular, provides background information on the channel representation, employed in Paper C.

3.1 Representations of visual information

The mapping of an image to another representation where the discriminative information for the specific task is maximized can significantly improve the performance and reduce the computational effort. The best choice of representation method is task dependant, which has led to the development of a plethora of different feature extraction and description techniques, e.g., the local descriptors SIFT [130], and BRIEF [37], and object template descriptors such as the HOG descriptor [46]. Representations can be hand-crafted based on a-priori knowledge about the problem (Paper E) or learned from data, for example in the layers of a Deep Neural Network [77].

Processing of high-dimensional data, such as images, is a difficult, computationally demanding problem. The so called *manifold hypothesis* justifies the use of representations for the purpose of automatic image analysis. The hypothesis states that real-world, natural, images lie on low-dimensional manifolds embedded in the high-dimensional space. Constraints arising from physical laws entail this low-dimensional structure [58]. Generative Adversar-

ial Networks [78] are examples of methods that exploit this fact in order to sample in this lower-dimensional space.

In some applications, parts of the image may be irrelevant to the solution of the problem. For example, the part above the horizon in the case of boat detection at sea (Paper C) and railway detection (Paper D). Images can also be represented in different color spaces, such as YUV or CIELAB (Paper G).

The purpose of the following sections is to introduce the reader to the *channel representation*, a biologically inspired, sparse, grid-based approach that fuses the concepts of histograms and wavelets. The channel representation provides a good compromise between hand-crafted descriptors and the a-priori structureless feature spaces that can be seen in the layers of deep networks [61].

3.2 Sparse representations

A *sparse* representation describes an input signal using only a few *active*, i.e., non-zero, units. Hence, most of the units of the representation are zero. In contrast, a *compact* representation method maximizes the information content in a minimum number of units, where all units are active. Examples of compact representations are dimensionality reduction techniques such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA) [156]. PCA is an orthogonal transformation of a set of samples into a smaller set of linearly uncorrelated principal components that maximize the variance of the data.

Sparse representations are often dictionary-based, i.e., each unit of the representation correspond to the coefficient of some basis function or element and a sample can be reconstructed by a linear combination of these. The Fourier-transform of a sinusoid is an example of a sparse representation. For other types of signals, the Fourier transform can be used to create sparse representations by setting all but a few of the coefficients to zero assuming that the original signal still can be represented sufficiently well [134]. This approach is, for example, employed by the JPEG image compression format [178].

3.3 Grid-based representations

A representation of a signal is *grid-based* if it maps the original signal on a regular (or irregular [79]) grid. Thus, a histogram, where the range of values is binned on a grid, would be considered as a grid-based representation. However, histogram-based representations often suffer from the lack of spatial information, an unfavourable property for some applications [61]. Other examples of grid-based representations are Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs) and Kernel Density Estimators (KDEs) [152].

Figure 3.1: Example of a (a) thermal infrared image, exploded into a distribution field using $N_b = 9$ bins. Images (b)-(j) display each one of the dimensions $n = 1, \dots, N_b$. The distribution field has been convolved with a Gaussian kernel with $\sigma = 1$ in the spatial and feature direction.

The idea behind the grid-based representation *Distribution Fields* [184] is to compute density estimates of the feature distribution on a regular grid. A Distribution Field (DF) is an N_{DF} -dimensional array. A 2D grayscale input image is *exploded* into a DF by increasing the dimension of the input array from 2 to $N_{DF} = 2 + D_F$ where the D_F dimensions index the chosen feature space. The ranges of the values of the feature space are binned using a histogram representation. In other words, in the case of intensity values ($D_F = 1$) as features, the DF is a three-dimensional array. Each pixel is extended to a histogram where each bin represents a range of intensity values from the original image, an example is provided in Fig. 3.1. In order to make the model robust to small changes, the DF is smoothed in the spatial and/or feature direction by a Gaussian kernel.

Distribution fields have been applied to the problems of image alignment [137] and visual object tracking [185]. The Distribution Field Tracker (DFT) [185] was later improved by Felsberg who proposed the Enhanced Distribution Field tracker (EDFT) [60]. The main aspect being the exchange from a histogram representation to channel vectors. Paper C extended the EDFT tracker to mitigate the problems of background contamination of the object model and object scale change.

3.4 Channel representations

The *channel representation* was proposed by Nordberg et al. [147], stemming from a biologically inspired information representation [79]. It is a sparse, grid-based, nonparametric approach that fuses the concepts of histograms and wavelets [61]. The channel representation share many similarities with popu-

Figure 3.2: (a) A thermal infrared image, channel encoded using $N = 9$ channels. Images (b)-(j) display the channel coefficients at each channel n .

lation codes in computational neuroscience [131, 160, 161], the relationship is further explained in [66].

The core idea of the channel representation is to represent values by their activations of overlapping shifted basis functions, so called *channels*, that are evenly placed along the range of the values. The channel representation can be seen as a soft histogram, sharing some similarities with the Average Shifted Histogram [183], that approximates a Kernel Density Estimator (KDE) [152] in a regular grid [59]. If Gaussian basis functions are used, the channel representation corresponds to the Radial Basis Functions [35] in machine learning [149]. Compared to a DF, channel representations apply a soft assignment, i.e., pre-smoothing, instead of post-smoothing of the bin assignments which has been shown to be more efficient [60].

The channel representation has been successfully used in many applications, e.g., point-set registration [49], object recognition [64], object segmentation [199], image denoising [63], and visual object tracking (Paper C) [47, 60, 150].

3.4.1 Channel encoding

A set of scalar samples x^m , where $m \in \{1, \dots, M\}$ is the sample index, can be channel encoded into a set of channel vectors \mathbf{c}^m using a basis of N channels. In the case of images, x^m is a function of spatial coordinates and the channel encoding is performed at each spatial location, i.e., pixel-wise, as illustrated in Fig. 3.2. Multi-dimensional channel encoding is also possible [100, 149], but out of scope for this thesis.

The channel encoding of a set of scalar samples x^m is a set of channel vectors $\mathbf{c}^m = [c_1^m, \dots, c_N^m]$ of channel coefficients c_n^m , where $n \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ is the index of the channels, ξ_n are the channel centers, and $K()$ is the encoding

Figure 3.3: Channel encoding of value $x = 4.2$ (black line). $N = 14$ quadratic B-spline basis functions are placed at $\xi_n \in \{0, 1, \dots, 13\}$. Three channels are active (solid lines) while the rest being inactive (dashed lines) resulting in the channel vector in Eq. 3.3.

kernel:

$$\mathbf{c}^m = \begin{bmatrix} c_1^m \\ \vdots \\ c_N^m \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} K(x^m - \xi_1) \\ \vdots \\ K(x^m - \xi_N) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3.1)$$

The *encoding kernel*, or basis function, $K()$ can be polynomial, exponential, or trigonometric [67]. A channel representation with a rectangular encoding kernel with no overlaps corresponds to a histogram [61]. The most common choices are Gaussian [191], B-spline [60], and windowed \cos^2 -kernels [150]. A quadratic B-spline kernel, employed in Paper C, is, for example, defined as:

$$K_B(x) = \begin{cases} 3/4 - x^2 & |x| \leq 1/2 \\ (|x| - 3/2)^2/2 & 1/2 < |x| \leq 3/2 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3.2)$$

The *channel coefficient* c_n^m is the *activation* of the basis function shifted to channel center ξ_n , see example in Fig. 3.3. In this example, the encoding kernel is a quadratic B-spline, Eq 3.2, and the $N = 14$ channel centers have been placed at $\xi_n \in \{0, 1, \dots, 13\}$. The channel encoding of $x = 4.2$, results in the channel vector:

$$\mathbf{c} = [0, 0, 0, 0.05, 0.71, 0.25, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]^T. \quad (3.3)$$

The value $x = 4.2$ (black line in Fig. 3.3) activates the basis functions with indices $n = 4, 5$, and 6 and c is, hence, naturally sparse.

The domain of the samples x^m is required to lie within the valid representable range \mathbb{A} of channel centers ξ_n :

$$\mathbb{A} = \{x^m \in \mathbb{R} : \xi_1 + \delta < x^m < \xi_N - \delta\} \quad (3.4)$$

If the samples x^m are not within the representable range \mathbb{A} , an appropriate transformation can be applied to x^m , or the spacing and width of the encoding

kernels adapted in order to fulfil this criteria. The offset δ depends on the width of the chosen basis function as well as the distance between channel centers and it ensures that each possible value of x^m activates an equal number of channels, $\delta = 0.5$ in the example in Fig. 3.3. The number of activated channels w for each value x^m can be chosen arbitrarily for the purpose of encoding. Motivated by the decoding [67], the standard choice has, however, been $w = 3$ [100]. A proof regarding minimal channel overlap is given in [149].

For the purpose of, e.g., visualization, the channel vectors need to be decoded. Channel *decoding* is, however, out of scope for this thesis. The interested reader is referred to [61, 149]. Decoding do infer some additional requirements on the shape of the basis function and the minimal channel overlap, as mentioned above. The necessary and sufficient conditions on the basis function for the purpose of decoding and representing distributions has been identified by Öfjäll [149].

In the case of limited ranges of discrete input samples x^m , for example pixel intensity values $\in [0, 255]$, the channel encodings for all possible values of x^m can be pre-computed and placed in a look-up table, enabling a computationally efficient representation.

3.4.2 Properties of channel vectors

The channel representation possess many useful properties, a few of them are mentioned here. First, since it is a sparse representation, multiple values can be represented in the same channel vector as:

$$\mathbf{c} = \begin{bmatrix} c_1 \\ \vdots \\ c_N \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{M} \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{m=1}^M c_1^m \\ \vdots \\ \sum_{m=1}^M c_N^m \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3.5)$$

Two encoded values located in opposite ends of the representable range can be separated when decoding the channel vector. If they are too close, decoding will provide an average of the two. The smallest distance between samples, the *metameric* distance, that the channel representation can handle is further investigated in [61, 67].

The basis functions of the channel representation are required to be non-negative, implying that also the channel coefficients of \mathbf{c} are non-negative. This in turn, implies that the sum of a channel vector is equal to the ℓ_1 norm:

$$\|\mathbf{c}\|_1 = \sum_{n=1}^N |c_n| = \sum_{n=1}^N c_n. \quad (3.6)$$

The sum of a channel vector for the \cos^2 and B-spline basis functions is constant as long as the encoded value lies within the representable range \mathbb{A} . For a quadratic B-spline, the sum of a channel vector equals to one, a property exploited in Paper C. Proofs of these properties are given in [67].

LEARNING METHODS

Learning is considered to be a major part of what is defined as human intelligence. Learning demonstrated by artificial systems, so called machine learning, is a subject of intense research frequently applied to problems within the field of computer vision. Machine learning methods enable us to define what a system should do, instead of how they should do it. The aim of this section is to provide background for the learning methods employed in Papers C, D, E, F, and G.

4.1 Intelligence and learning

Over the years, the definition of human intelligence has been focused on different aspects of the same. Psychologists have, however, agreed that the key to understanding intelligence is *adaptation*. A number of cognitive processes are required for effective adaptation, such as perception, memory, reasoning, problem solving, and *learning* [193]. Learning, as a part of intelligence, is a process that leads to change. As a consequence, concepts, ideas, and/or the world will be seen differently. Learning occurs as a result of experience and increases the potential for improved performance [7].

Artificial Intelligence (AI), is defined as human intelligence demonstrated by machines. The part of AI connected to learning is known as *machine learning*. Machine learning is introduced in Section 4.2, followed by some examples of machine learning properties and methods: online learning, Section 4.3, ensemble learning, Section 4.4, and neural networks, Section 4.5. The methods have been put into context in Fig. 4.1.

4.2 Introduction to machine learning

The history of machine learning dates back as early as the mid 18th century with the introduction of classical techniques such as Bayes' theorem (1763)

Figure 4.1: Deep learning techniques are a specific type of Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs). Together with ensemble methods, ANNs are a part of the more general topic of machine learning, and machine learning is in turn a part of the more general topic of artificial intelligence. Other types of machine learning methods exist as well, the purpose of this figure is to provide context for the methods described in this chapter.

[11] and the Least Squares method for data fitting (1805) [119], techniques that are fundamental for machine learning today. Machine learning, defined as the scientific study of systems that can learn from sample data, is a broad area that spans from linear curve fitting methods to complex non-linear algorithms such as deep neural networks. This section provides a short introduction to machine learning concepts utilized in the remainder of this chapter. The books by Bishop [29] and Hastie [82] provide a broader overview of the machine learning field.

The key to the success of any machine learning method is its ability to *generalize*. That is, its ability to make correct decisions when exposed to previously unseen data. Given a set of training samples represented in some feature space the task of a machine learning method is to find a mapping function $g : \mathbf{x} \mapsto \mathbf{y}$ from the space of inputs \mathbf{x} to the space of outputs \mathbf{y} . If this mapping is overly adapted to the training data, the algorithm will not generalize well.

4.2.1 Categorization of machine learning methods

Machine learning methods are categorized according to their properties and purpose. Some examples of common categorizations are presented below. Note that a machine learning method can possess more than one of these properties.

Figure 4.2: Illustrations of (a) classification, (b) regression, and (c) clustering.

Categorization based on input

Supervised learning methods have access to labelled training samples $(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{y}_1), \dots, (\mathbf{x}_T, \mathbf{y}_T)$ in contrast to **unsupervised** learning methods that only have unlabelled samples $\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_T$. Unsupervised methods learn the inherent structure of the input data. In the case of **reinforcement learning**, the input is accompanied with additional information, e.g., positive or negative feedback depending on the outcome of the method. If only a subset of the training samples are labelled, the method is **semi-supervised**. Finally, in **self-supervised** learning, training data is autonomously (or automatically) labelled. Methods such as autoencoders, Section 4.5.3, where the input is equal to the output are also categorized as self-supervised.

Categorization based on output

Classification methods find one or many decision boundaries and output discrete class labels. Conversely, **regression** methods have a continuous output. The aim of **clustering** methods is to discover structure in unlabelled data and, hence, they are typically unsupervised. Illustrations of these categorizations can be seen in Fig. 4.2.

Discriminative vs. generative methods

There are **discriminative** methods, such as classification algorithms, that model the decision boundary between classes. In contrast, **generative** models explicitly model the distribution of each class, i.e., for the purpose of clustering or image generation.

4.3 Online learning

Online learning is a property of machine learning methods rather than a method itself. In contrast to *offline* (or batch) learning methods, new training

data can be incorporated without retraining the full model [174]. In offline learning methods, the model is trained using the full set of training samples and, once completed, the parameters of the model are kept static and no further learning is permitted. In order for an offline method to incorporate new information, it has to be retrained using the new data samples together with all previous ones [99]. In the case of online machine learning, data becomes available in sequential order and the parameters of the model are updated continuously. The requirements for the computational demand and the memory usage do, however, vary between definitions [149].

In its simplest form, online machine learning can be the weighted average of the model \mathbf{m}^{t-1} at time $t-1$ and a new observation of the object \mathbf{o}^t , weighted by update factor $\alpha \in [0, 1]$:

$$\mathbf{m}^t = (1 - \alpha)\mathbf{m}^{t-1} + \alpha\mathbf{o}^t. \quad (4.1)$$

This convex combination update is employed in the methods presented in Papers C and D. The two methods are designed for different applications and use different representations. Paper C use a channel vector field while Paper D performs the update in the fourier domain. The simplicity of Eq. 4.1 is also its strength which makes it preferable in many applications.

While being particularly attractive solutions for large-scale, dynamically changing environments, online machine learning methods are prone to drift since they can be sensitive to sudden changes in the input. Their main advantage is, however, their ability to adapt to previously unseen data samples without retraining the whole model with the full set of training samples [99].

4.4 Ensemble learning

The term *ensemble learning*, refers to the combination of several weaker learning methods in order to increase the predictive performance compared to each constituent learning method alone. The weak learning method can be of any type, e.g., linear regression model, decision tree, neural network, etc. [175]. Two types of ensemble methods are evaluated in Paper E, AdaBoost and Random Forests.

The well-known Condorcet's jury theorem [42] states that for a jury of independent votes, the probability p_{jury} of the jury making the correct vote will be larger than the probability p of each individual voter to be correct, requiring $p > 0.5$. That is, $p > 0.5$ implies $p_{\text{jury}} > p$. Furthermore, $p_{\text{jury}} \rightarrow 1$ as the number of voters approaches infinity [167]. Hence, if the conditions are met, it is safe to assume that the combination of a sufficiently large set of weak learning methods with a performance slightly better than random, will increase the predictive performance compared to each one of the weak methods alone.

Different techniques can be used to increase the stability and accuracy of ensemble learning methods. One example is bootstrap aggregation, or *bagging*

Figure 4.3: An illustration of the AdaBoost algorithm. The weak classifiers $h_m(\mathbf{x})$ are trained sequentially using the training dataset \mathcal{D}_m with sample weights $d_m(t) \in [0, 1]$. The weights are updated before being fed to the next classifier. The strong classifier $H(\mathbf{x})$ weights the outputs of the weak classifiers using classifier weights α_m .

for short. Given a training set D and M number of weak learning methods, bagging generates M new training subsets D_m each one of the same size by sampling from D uniformly with replacement [32, 82]. The sampling can also be done based on prior information about the training samples. Each weak learning method is trained using a different subset D_m . Bagging has been shown to reduce the variance of the result and also the risk for overfitting [32]. The idea behind a different technique, known as *boosting*, is to train the weak learning methods in sequential order using the full training set D , but with weights indicating the importance of each sample. The first practical example of a boosting algorithm was the AdaBoost method, described below.

4.4.1 AdaBoost

Adaptive Boosting, or *AdaBoost*, is an ensemble boosting classification method proposed by Freund and Schapire [68]. The method combines M *weak* classifiers $h_m(\mathbf{x})$ into one *strong* classifier $H(\mathbf{x})$. The weak classifiers are often decision stumps, i.e., decision trees with a single split. The weak classifiers are trained sequentially and after each iteration the training sample weights $d_m(t)$ are updated. When combining all of the weak classifiers into a strong classifier, the weak classifiers are weighted using weights α_m . The training of the standard discrete AdaBoost algorithm is summarized in Algorithm 1 and illustrated in Fig. 4.3. There exists many other different types of boosting algorithms as well, a comprehensive summary is given by Schapire and Freund in [179].

Algorithm 1 Discrete AdaBoost training.

- 1: Given: $\mathcal{D}_m : \{(\mathbf{x}_t, y_t), d_m(t)\}_{t=1}^T$, where (\mathbf{x}_t, y_t) are the labelled training samples, $y_t \in \{-1, +1\}$, and $d_m(t) \in [0, 1]$ are the sample weights.
 - 2: Initialize: $d_1(t) = \frac{1}{T}$

 - 3: Iterate over the weak classifiers $h_m(\mathbf{x})$ and update sample weights $d_m(t)$:
 - 4: **for** $m = 1, \dots, M$ **do**
 - 5: Find weak classifier: $h_m(\mathbf{x}) = \{-1, +1\}$
 - 6: that minimizes: $\epsilon_m = \sum_{t=1}^T d_m(t) I(y_t \neq h_m(\mathbf{x}_t))$
 - 7: where $I(y_t \neq h_m(\mathbf{x}_t)) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } y_t \neq h_m(\mathbf{x}_t) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$
 - 8: Set: $\alpha_m = \frac{1}{2} \ln \frac{1-\epsilon_m}{\epsilon_m}$
 - 9: Update weights: $d_{m+1}(t) = d_m(t) e^{-\alpha_m y_t h_m(\mathbf{x}_t)}$
 - 10: Renormalize: $d_{m+1}(t) = \frac{d_{m+1}(t)}{\sum_{t=1}^T d_{m+1}(t)}$

 - 11: Output final hypothesis: $H(\mathbf{x}) = \text{sign}(\sum_{m=1}^M \alpha_m h_m(\mathbf{x}))$
-

4.4.2 Decision tree

A decision tree is a branching structure that partitions the feature space into a set of decision regions [82]. It is constituted by a *root* node, *internal* nodes, and *leaf* nodes. The internal nodes are the weak learners of this ensemble learning method. Each internal node applies an operation to a subset of the input dimensions and a threshold is then applied to the output in order to split the feature space [82]. The leaf nodes correspond to regions in the feature space to which some information or conclusion based on the input data has been assigned, e.g., classification labels. An example of a binary decision tree with a 2D-input can be seen in Fig. 4.4.

In theory, a decision tree of sufficient depth can describe any decision boundary, but an increased depth also increases the risk for overfitting. Therefore, the depth of a decision tree is in practice usually regulated by some stopping criterion while training. Decision trees can also be pruned in order to remove redundant sections for the purpose of complexity reduction and, hence, also reduction of the risk for overfitting [82].

4.4.3 Decision forest

A decision *forest* is an ensemble of decision trees. The most well-known decision forest is the *random forest* [33]. A random forest combines bagging with a random selection of features in each split. It has been shown that the generalization error for a random forest converges as the number of trees in

Figure 4.4: (a) A shallow decision tree with a 2D-input \mathbf{x} . (b) Each internal node partitions the feature space into a set of decision regions R_1, \dots, R_5 .

Figure 4.5: An artificial neuron is designed to mimic the features of a biological neuron. The activation function f is applied to the weighted sum of the inputs and the bias b , producing the output $y = f(\sum_{n=1}^N w_n x_n + b)$.

the forest becomes large [33]. All of the trees in a decision forest are generated independently, which makes it suitable for parallelization.

Decision forests are mainly used for the purpose of classification and regression, but can also be used for, e.g., clustering [187] and visual object detection [135].

4.5 Neural networks and deep learning

An Artificial Neural Network (ANN) is a biologically inspired machine learning method intended to replicate human intelligence. An ANN consists of a network of nodes, arranged in layers. The nodes are constituted by so called artificial *neurons*, designed to mimic the properties of a biological neuron, an example is provided in Fig. 4.5. The artificial neuron is a generalization of the *perceptron* architecture proposed by Rosenblatt in 1958 [169].

An artificial neuron is by itself a linear classifier, thus, suffering from the incapacity of correct classification of non-linearly separable data, e.g., the XOR-problem, as pointed out by Minsky and Papert in 1969 [139]. When

Figure 4.6: An example of a small, fully-connected, multi-layer, artificial neural network with two hidden layers. Each connection has a weight w_{ijk} , where the indices i, j , and k denote layer, node, and incoming connection.

combined into multi-layer networks, they do, however, become able to model non-linearities, provided a non-linear activation function. A multi-layer network with linear activations can be represented by a single layer, since a linear combination of linear functions is a linear function itself. Hence, a non-linear activation function is required. One of the early works of multi-layered architectures was the Neocognitron architecture proposed by Fukushima in the 1980's [70, 71]. An example of a shallow fully-connected¹ ANN is provided in Fig. 4.6.

ANNs are trained, i.e., the weights and biases for each node are updated based on the training samples, using the error *back-propagation* method [203]. The back-propagation method is a gradient-based optimization algorithm that exploits the chain rule of derivatives, thus, requiring the activation functions of the network to be differentiable² and non-linear.

The following sections introduce the reader to two specific types of neural networks, the autoencoder and the Generative Adversarial Network, employed in Papers F and G. The prerequisites for understanding these architectures are the concepts of *deep learning* and *Convolutional Neural Networks* explained below. For a more comprehensive summary of the history of Neural Networks, see, for example, the overview by Schmidhuber [182], and for the architectures, different types of layers and components etc., the deep learning book by Goodfellow et al. [77].

¹Each node is connected to all of the outputs of the previous layer.

²In practice, some non-differentiable functions can be used as well. For example, the popular ReLU function $f(x) = \max\{0, x\}$ which is not differentiable at $x = 0$.

4.5.1 Deep learning

Multi-layered neural networks with a large number of hidden layers came soon to be known as Deep Neural Networks (DNNs), and the specific type of machine learning as *deep learning* [77]. Despite the success of multi-layered neural networks, the progress was limited by computational speed and the amount of labelled data required for training. Motivated by this fact, Russakovsky et al. launched ImageNet [172], a free database of more than 14 million labelled images. The availability of large amounts of training data together with the significant speed-up of parallel processing hardware (GPUs), soon led to a rapid increase in both depth and complexity of published methods. Krizhevsky et al. proposed AlexNet [112], a Deep Convolutional (see Section 4.5.2) Neural Network with Rectified Linear Units (ReLU) as activation functions. AlexNet won several classification challenges in 2011 and 2012 outperforming its competitors. Shortly after, it was accompanied by VGG-16 [189], VGG-19 [189], ResNet [83], and GoogLeNet [195] just to mention a few.

Deep Neural Networks dominate many areas of signal processing and machine learning today. They have successfully been applied to many different applications, for example, early detection of skin cancer [57], restoration of colors in black and white photos [95], and semantic segmentation for the purpose of autonomous driving [186].

4.5.2 Convolutional Neural Networks

A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), is defined as a Deep Neural Network that uses convolutions instead of matrix multiplications in at least one of its layers [77]. Convolution layers in deep neural networks were proposed already by Fukushima in 1980 [71]. Ten years later, LeCun et al. successfully trained a CNN using back-propagation for the first time, the network was applied to handwritten zip code and digit recognition [116, 117]. CNNs are suitable for data with a grid-like topology, e.g., images, time-series, medical data etc.

Similarly to a fully-connected ANN, each *node* in each layer of a CNN receives as input every output from the previous layer, see example in Fig 4.7. The difference lies in the design of the node. Instead of a set of single neurons as nodes, each layer of a standard CNN consists of nodes that contain three parts, inspired by the early findings about the mammal visual system by Hubel and Wiesel [93]. First, the input is *convolved* (or correlated [77]) using a filter, or *convolution kernel*, producing a set of linear activations. Each node of the layer has a different kernel. The convolution is followed by a non-linearity, an *activation function* and, finally, a pooling operation is applied to the output *feature map*. A pooling operation replaces the feature map at certain locations with a summary of the statistic of the nearby locations. A common pooling operation is, for example, max pooling [215] that extracts the maximum value within a rectangular neighbourhood. Max pooling reduces the dimensionality

Figure 4.7: An example of a small Convolutional Neural Network with two convolution layers and a 2D-array input \mathbf{X} and output \mathbf{Y} . Each node of a convolution layer consists of a convolution $*$, a non-linear activation f , and a pooling operation \mathbf{P} .

of the feature map, provides invariance to small translations, while at the same time reducing the risk for overfitting [77]. Additional techniques that can be used for increased stability and faster training are, e.g., batch normalization [97, 177] and regularization by dropout [192].

Each node of a CNN is constituted by a spatial grid of neurons and each neuron receives as input the values from a local neighbourhood, the *receptive field*. The local neighbourhood has the same size as the convolution kernel. The weights, or kernel coefficients, are shared among the neurons in the same node, enabling efficient training. As layers are stacked, the receptive field of a neuron is enlarged. Neurons in the final layer of a CNN may be *indirectly* connected to all of the neurons in the first layer. An example is provided in Fig. 4.8.

As mentioned above, the architecture of a CNN was inspired by the visual processing found in the primary visual cortex of the mammal brain. Hubel and Wiesel [92, 93] examined the neurons in the primary visual cortex of a cat and discovered two different kinds of cells, simple and complex. The convolutions in a CNN correspond to the simple cells and the pooling to the complex cells [71]. In later years, CNN visualization techniques have been able to confirm that the convolution layers indeed represent increasingly complex visual features as we move up in the visual hierarchy, similar to the mammal visual system [36, 56, 188, 209].

4.5.3 Autoencoders

The idea of using neural networks for representation learning and, more specifically, designing a network in such a way that a compressed representation of the original input is imposed, may have emerged as early as 1987 [182]. These networks, known as *autoencoders*, enable efficient learning of compact

Figure 4.8: The receptive field (highlighted) of a neuron in the final layer of a Convolutional Neural Network is enlarged as the total number of layers is increased. In this example, the convolution kernel has width 3 and the neuron n_{33} is indirectly connected to all of the neurons in the input layer. Padding techniques, dashed neurons, can be added at the borders in order to maintain the size of the feature map. The figure was inspired by Fig. 9.4 in [77].

representations. The general architecture of an autoencoder is presented in Fig. 4.9a. An autoencoder can be seen as a nonlinear generalization of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) [77].

While training, input samples \mathbf{x} are propagated through an *encoder* $\mathcal{E}(\mathbf{x}; \theta_{\mathcal{E}})$, $\mathcal{E} : \mathbf{x} \mapsto \mathbf{z}$ with parameters $\theta_{\mathcal{E}}$. The output of the encoder is the latent vector \mathbf{z} . Subsequently, \mathbf{z} is propagated through a *decoder* $\mathcal{C}(\mathbf{z}; \theta_{\mathcal{C}})$, $\mathcal{C} : \mathbf{z} \mapsto \hat{\mathbf{x}}$. The aim is to minimize the reconstruction error $\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, \hat{\mathbf{x}})$, usually defined as a distance function between \mathbf{x} and $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$. The architecture of the encoder \mathcal{E} may vary and have an arbitrary number of layers that decrease the dimensionality of the input signal. The architecture of the decoder \mathcal{C} is typically inverted compared to \mathcal{E} and instead increases resolution while reconstructing the signal.

In order for \mathbf{z} to become a compact representation of the input data, the output signal $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ should be identical to the input signal \mathbf{x} , and the dimension of \mathbf{z} should be less than the dimension of \mathbf{x} . If the dimensions are equal, the network could just learn to copy the values along the network. The challenge with autoencoders lies in finding *meaningful* compact representations that generalize well to unseen data. There are several regularization techniques for this purpose. For example, sparse autoencoders [133] in which activations are penalized during training, and denoising autoencoders [198] where noise is added to the input signal in the training phase.

Since the input signal \mathbf{x} should be identical to the output signal $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$, the problem at hand is neither supervised nor unsupervised. Therefore, autoencoder training is often referred to as *self-supervised* representation learning. The learnt encoder can, e.g., be used as a feature descriptor, or, in combination with the decoder, for signal compression and decompression.

Figure 4.9: (a) The general structure of an autoencoder architecture. An autoencoder consists of an encoder \mathcal{E} and a decoder \mathcal{C} network. The output of \mathcal{E} is the latent vector \mathbf{z} , a compressed representation of the input signal \mathbf{x} . (b) The general structure of a U-Net architecture. So called skip connections have been added to the traditional autoencoder structure and the output signal \mathbf{y} is not required to be identical to the input signal \mathbf{x} .

While minimizing the reconstruction error, comparing inputs to outputs, autoencoders learn the density of a data distribution rather than the distribution itself, i.e., they do not have a probabilistic interpretation. Therefore, autoencoders are not considered to be generative models. The latent space in which the encoded vectors lie may not be continuous and a random \mathbf{z} may lie in a discontinuity, generating unrealistic outputs. In contrast, so called *variational* autoencoders (VAEs) [103] estimate the parameters of a data distribution and can, thus, generate unseen samples from the same distribution.

Architectures similar to autoencoders, where the encoder-decoder structure remains, but the output signal $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ is not identical to the input signal \mathbf{x} , are common as well. One example is the U-Net architecture [168], an example is provided in Fig. 4.9b. In contrast to the standard autoencoder structure, the output \mathbf{y} is not identical to the input \mathbf{x} and there are so called *skip connections* between the encoder and the decoder. A skip connection appends all channels at layer i with those at layer $I - i$ (where I is the total number of layers). These connections ensure that the features learnt while contracting the signal are also considered when reconstructing it. U-Net type architectures have been used, e.g., for grayscale colorization [98], image segmentation [10], and modality transfer (Paper G).

This section has only provided a brief overview of autoencoders. Autoencoders can, and have been, used in numerous different configurations and applications. For more information on autoencoders and VAEs, see, for example, the overviews by Bengio and Courville [12], and Tschannen et al. [197].

Figure 4.10: The general structure of a Generative Adversarial Network (GAN). A GAN consists of a generator \mathcal{G} and a discriminator \mathcal{D} .

4.5.4 Generative Adversarial Networks

At first sight, a Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) somewhat resembles an autoencoder turned inside out, Fig. 4.10. Taking a closer look, there are, however, significant objective and implementation differences. In its original formulation [78], a GAN consists of two fully-connected networks; a generator \mathcal{G} and a discriminator \mathcal{D} .

A GAN can model complex, high-dimensional data distributions [44]. Behind the theory of GANs lies the assumption that there exist a lower dimensional subspace in which the training samples $\mathbf{x}_{\text{data}} \sim p_{\text{data}}(\mathbf{x})$ can be represented, the so called latent space. The aim of a GAN is to find a mapping $\mathcal{G} : \mathbf{z} \mapsto \mathbf{x}_g$ from the latent space, a prior $\mathbf{z} \sim p_z(\mathbf{z})$, to generated samples $\mathbf{x}_g \sim p_g(\mathbf{x})$ for which the two distributions p_g and p_{data} overlap. $p_{\text{data}}(\mathbf{x})$ denotes the probability density function over a random vector \mathbf{x} that lies in $\mathbb{R}^{|\mathbf{x}|}$.

This mapping $\mathcal{G}(\mathbf{z} : \theta_{\mathcal{G}})$ with parameters $\theta_{\mathcal{G}}$ is found by training the generator \mathcal{G} and the discriminator \mathcal{D} alternately. The objective of $\mathcal{D}(\mathbf{x} : \theta_{\mathcal{D}})$, $\mathcal{D} : \mathbf{x} \mapsto \mathbf{y}$ is to correctly classify input samples \mathbf{x} as samples coming from $p_g(\mathbf{x})$ or $p_{\text{data}}(\mathbf{x})$, while the objective of \mathcal{G} is to fool \mathcal{D} . As training proceeds, \mathcal{D} will improve its classification skills while, at the same time, \mathcal{G} will become better at generating samples similar to the original data. In other words, the aim is to find the Nash equilibrium of this non-convex minmax two-player game [176].

Hence, the objective, or loss function, of a standard GAN is defined as:

$$\min_{\theta_{\mathcal{G}}} \max_{\theta_{\mathcal{D}}} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x} \sim p_{\text{data}}(\mathbf{x})} q(\mathcal{D}(\mathbf{x})) + \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{z} \sim p_z(\mathbf{z})} q(1 - \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{G}(\mathbf{z}))) \quad (4.2)$$

where $q(\mathbf{x}) = \log(\mathbf{x})$ in the original formulation [78]. In practice, \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{D} are trained and updated alternately. GAN training has proven to be cumbersome, and improved techniques have been proposed. Radford et al. [162] used convolutional instead of fully-connected layers (Deep Convolutional GAN, DCGAN), and Salimans et al. [176] suggested some tips and tricks that could be used to further improve stability. Among other things, DCGANs are, however, known to suffer from mode collapse [8]. In order to mitigate these problems, Arjovsky et al. [8] proposed to use a Wasserstein loss (WGAN) instead

of Eq. 4.2. Improved training techniques for WGANs were later proposed by Gulrajani et al. [81] (WGAN-GP). Progressive Growing GANs (progGAN) [102] progressively add layers that increase resolution while training. Some examples of thermal infrared images generated using a progGAN can be seen in Fig. 4.11. This summary is only a brief review, for more information, see, e.g., [76, 113, 200, 201].

Several alterations to the original GAN architecture have been proposed for different applications. For example, conditional GANs [140] (cGAN) that use extra label information while training, and InfoGANs [39] that can learn disentangled representations. There are GANs suitable for clustering [142], image-to-image translation [217], image super resolution [118], image inpainting [128], anomaly detection (Paper F), and many more.

Inverting the generator

In contrast to autoencoders, standard GANs do not possess the ability of mapping back from an observation \mathbf{x} to a latent, compressed, representation \mathbf{z} . In GAN terminology, this mapping is sometimes known as an *inference mechanism*. A GAN inference mechanism can be useful, e.g., for discriminative tasks such as classification, manipulation of images [157, 216], or providing interesting insights to what a trained GAN has learned [43]. There are two main approaches to GAN inference; introducing an additional neural network, an *encoder*, or formulating the inversion as an optimization problem. Each one is described in further detail below.

When introducing an additional neural network, an encoder $\mathcal{E}(\mathbf{x} : \theta_{\mathcal{E}})$, $\mathcal{E} : \mathbf{x} \mapsto \mathbf{z}_e$, there are two options. The encoder can either be trained in hindsight as in, e.g., [180] or trained simultaneously (Paper F) [54, 55]. Simultaneous training, although not applicable to pre-trained models, was advocated by Donahue, Dumoulin et al. [54, 55]. Donahue et al. [54] (BiGAN) and concurrent work by Dumoulin et al. [55] (ALI) proposed similar architectures, Fig. 4.12a. Tuples of observations and encoded samples $(\mathbf{x}_{\text{data}}, \mathbf{z}_e)$ or generated samples and prior $(\mathbf{x}_g, \mathbf{z})$ are fed to the discriminator \mathcal{D} during training. The objective of the discriminator \mathcal{D} is to determine if the joint pairs originates from the original or generated distribution. The generator \mathcal{G} and encoder \mathcal{E} are trained jointly. Various training strategies to learn an encoder was explored by Dumoulin et al. [55], although on a very specific set of problems, and they emphasized the importance of learning \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{E} jointly.

These networks, BiGAN and ALI, are trained for the purpose of accurate recovery of latent vectors. Depending on the purpose and application, the design and implementation of both architecture and objective function may change. For example, Mukherjee et al. [142] added an encoder trained jointly with the generator in order to improve the clustering performance of their network (ClusterGAN), the architecture can be seen in Fig. 4.12b. The employed objective function compared distances in the *latent space* rather than

(a) Real images

(b) Generated images

Figure 4.11: Examples of a) real and b) generated aerial thermal infrared image patches using a Progressive Growing GAN.

Figure 4.12: Examples of two different GAN inference mechanisms. Encoders \mathcal{E} map from an observation \mathbf{x} to latent vector \mathbf{z} . a) BiGAN [54] and ALI [55] inputs tuples of observations and encoded samples $(\mathbf{x}_{\text{data}}, \mathbf{z}_e)$ or generated samples and prior $(\mathbf{x}_g, \mathbf{z})$ to the discriminator \mathcal{D} . b) ClusterGAN [142] (no dashed line) and Paper F (dashed line) instead trains the encoder \mathcal{E} jointly with \mathcal{G} , employing an encirclement loss.

the image space. For anomaly detection, Schlegl et al. [180] instead showed that an objective function where distances in *image space* are compared was preferable. This was also confirmed in Paper F.

There are some disadvantages associated with an additional encoder network. First, additional parameters have to be trained, leading to an increased risk for the network to overfit [195] or to memorize samples [96]. Second, encoder networks trained jointly with the generator and discriminator can not be applied to pre-trained GANs and are, thus, not useful for GAN evaluation. Lipton et al. [127] instead suggest to use Stochastic Gradient Descent in combination with gradient clipping to search for the closest match for observation x in latent space, yielding the following optimization problem:

$$\min_{\mathbf{z}'} \|\mathbf{x} - \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{z}')\|_2^2 \quad (4.3)$$

where \mathbf{z}' is a random latent variable over which Eq. 4.3 is optimized. Gradient descent then performs the update $\mathbf{z}' \leftarrow \mathbf{z}' - \eta \nabla_{\mathbf{z}'} \|\mathbf{x} - \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{z}')\|_2^2$. A similar approach is proposed by Creswell et al. [43]. Formulating the inversion as an optimization problem provides accurate results but suffers from computational inefficiency [180, 181].

One might ask how these GAN inference networks differ from variational autoencoders (VAEs). Why not use a VAE instead since it already includes an inference mechanism? Depending on the application, a VAE may indeed be a better choice of generative model. VAEs are, however, known to produce samples of lower quality than those generated by GAN-based approaches [115, 162]. Image samples from VAE-trained models tend to be blurry since VAEs suffer from a well-recognized issue of the maximum likelihood training paradigm [55]. A VAE learns the probability distribution *explicitly* while a GAN learns an *implicit* distribution.

ADDRESSED PROBLEMS WITHIN THERMAL INFRARED IMAGE ANALYSIS

As thermal cameras become more widely used in civilian applications, the need for effective methods for automatic image analysis in thermal infrared images increases. In this chapter, three different problems are addressed: visual object tracking, anomaly detection, and modality transfer. The problem of modality transfer is described in the context of cross-spectral transfer learning. The following chapter introduces the reader to these three problems and describes their relevance to real-world applications. The chapter also explains the difference between different types of tracking, describes how correlation filters can be used for obstacle detection, and shows examples of large piles of biofuel being classified as beds.

5.1 Visual object tracking

The general problem of tracking can be defined as the identification of an object trajectory over time. The trajectory can be represented either by the object's positions at each time step or its shape. An *object* is defined as anything that might be of interest for further analysis, e.g., humans, vehicles, or chocolate. The choice of representation of the trajectory depends on the application. The object shape is, for example, typically required for object classification while virtual fences (intrusion alarms) only require object positions. Parts of this section are revised versions of parts of Section 3.3 in the author's licentiate thesis [25].

Figure 5.1: An illustration of the differences between a) target tracking, b) extended target tracking, and c) visual object tracking. The first row shows measurements (red points and squares) at time t and the second row measurements at time $t + 1$. The figure was inspired by Fig. 1. in [80].

5.1.1 Difference between tracking and tracking

It is important not to confuse *visual object tracking* with *target tracking*. Target tracking is defined as the prediction of future locations of a dynamical system based on its estimates and measurements. A *target* is defined as anything whose state is of interest, similar to the definition of an *object* within the computer vision field. Within the field of target tracking, there are two main assumptions on the target: the target can be modelled as a point and it gives rise to at most one single measurement per time step [80]. Hence, target tracking is applied to point measurements in one or many different sensors. The sensors can be of any type, microphone, LiDAR, GPS, etc. The problem then lies in the *association* of the measurements. A highly complex problem due to sensor noise, missed detections, clutter detections, and measurement origin uncertainty.

There are, however, a variety of scenarios for which the two point assumptions are not valid. Tracking of targets that occupy more than one sensor cell is known as *extended target tracking*. In extended target tracking, the target gives rise to a varying number of potentially noisy measurements from different spatially distributed measurement sources. In contrast to regular target tracking, the aim is not only to estimate the target's state but also its shape [80].

Visual object tracking, as opposed to extended target tracking, refers to tracking of extended objects in the *image domain*. In addition, the number

of measurements (pixels) per object per time-step is usually high in contrast to extended target tracking where the measurements are few and sparse. The aim of visual object tracking is to locate a certain object in all frames of a video, given only its location in the first frame. A visual object tracking method typically stores a model of the object appearance which is updated continuously. Illustrations of the differences between target tracking, extended target tracking, and visual object tracking can be seen in Fig. 5.1.

Within the field of visual object tracking, there are subdivisions depending on the type of problem. For example, there are short/long-term, single/multi-target, and single/multi-sensor tracking methods. This thesis focuses on the problem of short-term, single-object, single-sensor visual object tracking. Short-term means that only short periods of time, a couple of minutes maximum, are considered, and also that there is no requirement of re-identification of objects.

5.1.2 Challenges of visual object tracking

There are a number of different challenges associated with visual object tracking [110, 204, 208]. First of all, there is a loss of information caused by the projection of the 3D world on a 2D image. This loss makes, for example, the handling of occlusions more difficult. Partial or full object occlusions may appear due to other objects in the scene or self-occlusion by the object itself. The effects can be mitigated by using multi-camera or multi-sensor systems to help with depth information.

Complex and unpredictable object and/or camera motion might lead to motion blur and difficulties in modelling of object motion. Properties of the scene affect the degree of difficulty as well. There can be scene illumination changes and background clutter, that is, background in the vicinity of the object that has similar appearance. Complex object shapes, scale variations, and aspect ratio changes due to the non-rigid nature of some objects may aggravate accurate tracking of objects even further. In addition, there might be image noise and real-time processing requirements.

Common ways to reduce the complexity of the tracking problem at hand is to use motion and/or appearance constraints (when applicable) as well as to utilize prior knowledge about the object appearance to pre-train an object model.

5.1.3 Template-based tracking

Template-based tracking is a visual object tracking technique where an example image patch of the object, a template, is extracted in the first frame. The template constitutes an initial object model. In each new frame, the tracker finds the region that best matches the object and updates the object model.

Figure 5.2: An overview of a typical template-based tracking technique where a model \mathbf{m}^t of the object is updated in each time-step. Variations of the flowchart exist as well.

A template-based tracking method designed specifically for thermal infrared images is presented in Paper C.

The principle of template-based tracking techniques is illustrated in Fig. 5.2. When designing a template-based tracking method, several decisions have to be made, such as the choice of a object region, a representation of appearance, a representation of motion and position, as well as a method for measuring similarity, optimization and template update. Each one of these areas are described more thoroughly below.

Object region: The most common choice for representation of the object region is the bounding box. The bounding box is advantageous due to its simple representation (position, width, and height), but in most cases, it does not represent the object well. A majority of the area inside the bounding box can even be background and not object depending on the object shape. However, to a certain extent, including background in the object model can be beneficial since the background/object contrast can provide valuable information. Approaches where object and non-object areas inside a bounding box are identified and the information incorporated in the tracking have been proposed, for example, in Paper C and by Ning et al. [146]. Other commonly used object regions are: ellipses, contours, blobs, patches, salient features, parts, and multiple bounding boxes [190].

Representation of appearance: Representation of object appearance basically boils down to the question of how to represent the object pixel intensity values in order to preserve spatial and temporal information. The representation can be N -dimensional and correspond to a 2D-array of image data, a 1D-histogram of ordered properties, or an N -dimensional feature vector. The simplest approach is to use the raw pixel intensity values themselves, as in, e.g., the Normalized Cross-Correlation tracker [34]. Examples of other representations are histograms, discriminative correlation filters, kernel density estimators [183], channel representations [79, 147], and deep features. Combinations of different features and representations are also possible.

Some trackers also consider scale variations and, in that case, information about object appearance at a larger scale should preferably be kept since crucial information might be lost during downsampling.

Representation of motion and position: A common choice of motion representation is to use linear or non-linear dynamic models in the form of state space models like the Kalman or Particle filters. The motion prediction is typically used to provide an initial estimate of the position in order to limit the search space. In many cases, the constant position/velocity motion model has proven to be sufficient.

Search method/similarity measurement: An initial guess for the search method is typically provided by the motion prediction. Search methods can either be exhaustive or heuristic, and are usually limited by real-time processing requirements. Heuristic methods risk being stuck in local minima.

The choice of similarity measure depends on the choice of appearance representation. Generative tracking methods, for example, use a distance measurement that measures the distance from a tentative patch to the target distribution in feature space. Another example are methods based on correlation filters that search for the best matching patch and measures similarity via convolution.

Template update: A naïve assumption is that the object appearance remains the same throughout the entire sequence. This assumption can be valid for short periods of time, but eventually, due to changes in viewpoint and lighting as well as non-rigid object motion, the initial object model will generally not be an accurate representation of the object appearance. How to correctly update the object model is one of the greatest challenges within template-based tracking. The so called *template update problem* has been described by, e.g., Matthews et al. [136]. It implies that small errors that are merged into the object model during update accumulates over time, causing the tracker to drift.

The choice of update strategy typically depends on the choice of object region as well as the representation of appearance. A common approach is to use a simple linear adaptive update scheme where the object model at time t , \mathbf{m}^t , is updated by weighting together the object model at time $t - 1$, \mathbf{m}^{t-1} and the best matching object patch \mathbf{z}^t as

$$\mathbf{m}^t = (1 - \alpha)\mathbf{m}^{t-1} + \alpha\mathbf{z}^t, \quad (5.1)$$

using a weight $\alpha \in [0, 1]$. The model \mathbf{m} and patch \mathbf{z} are all in the chosen representation. Non-linear weighting approaches exist as well. The problem with adaptive update strategies is that they have a quite short memory span. Other update strategies that use learning methods, i.e. discriminative tracking techniques, can have longer memory spans.

5.1.4 Tracking benchmarks and datasets

Visual object tracking is a challenging problem [74, 125, 141] that has attracted significant attention in the past two decades. Established methodologies for performance evaluation are necessary to assess the advances within the field. Several initiatives have been made to establish a common ground in tracking performance evaluation, such as PETS [210], the Visual Object Tracking (VOT) challenges [105, 106, 107, 108, 109, 110, 111] and the Object Tracking Benchmark [204, 205]. Within the area of thermal infrared tracking, far fewer benchmarks and datasets exist. Those that do are described below.

Benchmarks

There are, to the best of the authors knowledge, only two initiatives that include challenges on tracking in thermal infrared images. The series of workshops on Performance Evaluation of Tracking and Surveillance (PETS) included TIR tracking in the challenges organized in 2005 [210], 2015 [124], 2016 [153], and 2017 [154]. The challenge was detection, multi-camera/long-term tracking and behavior (threat) analysis in contrast to the other initiative organized in conjunction with the Visual Object Tracking challenge (VOT). The VOT-TIR 2015 [62], VOT-TIR 2016 [65], and VOT-RGBT 2019 [106] challenges instead focused on the problem of short-term tracking. The author was part of the data collection of thermal infrared sequences for PETS 2015, 2016, and 2017, as well as VOT-TIR 2015, and 2016. The multi-modal semi-automatic annotation process that was utilized to create the dataset for VOT-RGBT 2019 is presented in Paper B.

VOT-TIR, introduced in 2015, was the first thermal infrared, short-term tracking challenge. Like the VOT challenge, the VOT-TIR challenge considered single-camera, single-target, model-free, causal trackers, applied to short-term tracking. That is, pre-built object models and incorporation of information from future frames were prohibited. VOT-TIR was featured as a sub-challenge to VOT2015, organized in conjunction with ICCV2015. The challenge enabled participants not only to evaluate their results on visual data, but also to benchmark their trackers on thermal infrared sequences. The VOT-TIR2015 challenge was based on the LTIR-dataset introduced in Paper A. The main idea of VOT-TIR was to carry the idea of an established evaluation methodology to the area of thermal infrared data. In VOT-TIR 2016 [65], the LTIR dataset was updated with new, more challenging sequences. For VOT-RGBT 2019, the VOT committee decided to make a community-driven move towards the combination of RGB and thermal sequences (RGBT) and a new dataset was needed. A multi-modal semi-automatic annotation method (Paper B) was developed for this purpose.

Table 5.1: Properties of the currently available civilian datasets for benchmarking of TIR- and RGB-T-tracking methods. λ denotes the wavelength band (LWIR/MWIR), Bpp is the number of bits per pixel, and $Stat/Mov$ indicates if the sequences in the dataset were recorded using a static and/or moving camera. This table is an updated version of the table appearing in the author’s licentiate thesis [25].

Type	Name	#Seq	Tot #frames	Resolution	λ	Bpp	Stat/Mov	Published
TIR	OSU-TP [50]	10	0.2k	360 × 240	L	8	Y/N	2005
	Terravic Motion [138]	20	23.3k	320 × 240	L	8	Y/N	2006
	ASL-TID [159]	9	4.3k	324 × 256	L	8/16	N/Y	2014
	BU-TIV [206]	16	64k	Up to 1024 × 1024	M	16	Y/N	2014
	LTIR (Paper A)	20	11.2k	Up to 1920 × 480	L	8/16	Y/Y	2015
	PTB-TIR [129]	60	30.1k	Up to 1280 × 720	?	8	Y/Y	2018
	OSU-CT [51]	6	17k	360 × 240	L	8	Y/N	2007
RGB-T	LITIV [196]	9	6.3k	320 × 240	L	8	Y/N	2012
	KAIST-MS [94]	41	95k	640 × 512 (320 × 256)	L	8	N/Y	2015
	GTOT [121]	50	15.8k	400 × 296	L	8	Y/N	2016
	RGBT210 [123]	210	210k	630 × 460	L	8	Y/Y	2017
	CAMEL [75]	30	44.5k	336 × 256	L	8	Y/Y	2018
	RGBT234 [122]	234	233.8k	630 × 460	L	8	Y/Y	2018

Datasets

Compared to the amount of available datasets for evaluation of tracking methods in the visual domain, the number of available datasets for tracking evaluation in thermal infrared images is small. In the absence of relevant datasets, researchers will start evaluating their methods on proprietary datasets, making it difficult to get an overview of advancements made in the field. A summary of currently available *civilian* thermal infrared datasets for benchmarking of tracking methods is provided in Table 5.1. Snapshots from each dataset are presented in Fig. 5.3.

In summary, the number of sequences per dataset, the total number of frames, and the resolution of thermal infrared tracking datasets have increased in the last couple of years. The included sequences have also become more challenging, with an increasing number of sequences featuring, e.g., occlusions, distractors, and objects with apparent temperatures similar to the background. There are, however, still only a few datasets available in 16-bits per pixel: LTIR (Paper A) and ASL-TID [159].

5.1.5 Tracking in thermal infrared images

There are two common beliefs regarding visual object tracking in thermal infrared images. The first is that it is all about tracking warm objects against cold backgrounds, so called *hotspot* tracking. This assumption is valid for certain applications only, e.g., tracking aircrafts against a cold sky, but for most other applications the situation is more complex. For example, in a surveillance application, the object can be warmer than the background initially, but as the day progresses and the sun rises and heats the surroundings, the object will soon be colder than the background. At some point, the object and the background will even have the same apparent temperature.

The second common belief is that tracking in thermal infrared is identical to tracking in grayscale visual images. Consequently, a good tracker designed for visual images should also be a good tracker for thermal infrared. In Paper A and VOT-TIR 2015 [62] it was shown that hotspot tracking is applicable to specific applications only and benchmarks were performed where the relative ranking of the participating trackers were different on visual (RGB) and thermal infrared sequences.

Tracking in thermal infrared vs. visual images

The characteristics of thermal infrared (TIR) imagery and how they differ from those of visual imagery were described in Section 2.4. The described differences indicate that tracking in TIR images is not identical to tracking in grayscale visual images. Listed below are the differences between the two types of imagery that affect the design of a TIR tracking method.

Figure 5.3: Snapshots from all datasets listed in Table 5.1 cropped to have equal height/width ratio. (a)-(f) are TIR datasets and (g)-(m) are RGB-T datasets.

- **Noise characteristics:** A tracker that depends heavily on (high resolution) spatial structure is presumably suboptimal for TIR images since such images have different noise characteristics, e.g., lower resolution and more blooming.
- **Shadows:** The absence of shadows might make a tracker designed to handle shadows in the visual domain suboptimal for TIR images.
- **Spatial patterns:** Visual colour patterns are discernible in the thermal infrared spectrum only if they correspond to variations in material or temperature. Thus, re-identification and resolving occlusions might have to be done differently. For example, two persons with differently patterned or coloured clothes might look similar in TIR images.
- **Emitted vs. reflected radiation:** Trackers that exploit the absolute levels should have an advantage in TIR images due to the fact that the emitted radiation change much slower than the reflected radiation in most applications. Examples of such trackers are trackers based on distribution fields and the tracker described in Paper C.
- **16-bit data:** Trackers that are able to exploit 16-bit data from radiometric cameras should have an advantage since they have a dynamic range large enough to accommodate relevant temperature intervals without adapting the dynamic range to each frame.
- **Colour features:** There is no colour in TIR images and trackers relying on colour features are, therefore, not suitable. Video-rate multispectral thermal cameras exist but they are rare and out of scope of this thesis.

5.2 Anomaly detection

Anomaly, or outlier, detection is the identification of *rare* samples, objects, or events that can be regarded as anomalous compared to what is considered to be normal [90]. In the context of machine learning, anomaly detection can be *supervised*, *semi-supervised*, or *unsupervised*. By definition, the percentage of anomalies in a dataset is small, usually less than 1%. Therefore, unsupervised methods are commonly used to address the problem.

The objective of unsupervised anomaly detection is to detect unseen, rare, objects or events without any prior knowledge about these. Since anomalies are rare and unknown to the user at training time, anomaly detection in most cases boils down to the problem of modelling the normal data distribution and defining a measurement in this space in order to classify samples as anomalous or normal, this is illustrated in Fig. 5.4. Classical methods model the data distribution, e.g., by using a non-parametric Kernel Density Estimator (KDE) [152] as in [207] where it is applied to intrusion detection. Samples in low

Figure 5.4: Anomaly detection in most cases boils down to the problem of modelling the distribution of normal samples. A distance measurement is then defined in this space and all samples outside a certain decision boundary (dashed line) are classified as anomalies.

density areas are treated as anomalies. In high-dimensional data such as images, distances in the original space quickly lose descriptive power due to the curse of dimensionality and a mapping to a more suitable, lower dimensional, space is required.

The problem of anomaly detection, as such, is quite general and, therefore, it can be found in a wide range of different fields, e.g., agriculture [40], medicine [180, 181], and finance [1, 4]. Three of the included papers (Paper D, E, and F) employ different types of unsupervised anomaly detection, all of which are introduced in the following sections. Section 5.2.2 previously appeared in the author’s licentiate thesis [25].

5.2.1 Background subtraction

Background subtraction, also known as change detection, is an example of an anomaly detection problem. A model of the background is automatically learnt and all samples not belonging to what is defined as background are classified as foreground, or anomalies. Background subtraction is a broad research topic and a complete review of techniques is out of scope for this thesis.

In Paper E, the detection of district heating leakages is treated as an anomaly detection, or background subtraction problem. Thermal images are acquired from an aircraft, Fig. 5.5a and 5.5b, during the night or dawn. Data collection during the day would complicate the detection task due to sun heating effects. The media (water or steam) inside district heating pipes is warm, implying that a damaged pipe leaking media would also heat its surroundings. The temperature difference between the background and a district heating media leakage can be visualized by a high-end, cooled, thermal

Figure 5.5: Detection of potential district heating leakages in thermal infrared images. (a) A high-end thermal infrared camera mounted in an aircraft acquires (b) a set of thermal infrared images covering an area. Pixel intensity values of all pixels inside a binary heat pipe image mask forms (c) a histogram, estimating the distribution of normal intensity variations $p_T(x)$. Intensities in the upper tail are treated as anomalies (red area), possibly due to media (water or steam) leakages. (d) Example of visualization of a media leakage.

camera. The flight height and speed put certain requirements on the employed sensor, hence, a high-end *cooled* sensor is used.

The background of each acquisition flight is modelled by the pixel intensity distribution $p_T(x)$, a model of the normal variations of pixel intensity values. Since real leakages are rare, $p_T(x)$ is estimated, without significant bias, by the histogram of all intensity values under a binary image mask of the district heating pipe network, Fig. 5.5c. The pipe mask is found by projecting the GIS-layer of pipe locations onto the corresponding registered thermal images [69].

Media leakages are expected to cause higher surface temperatures than what is normal. They are, thus, outliers with respect to $p_T(x)$ and are assumed to be found in the upper tail of $p_T(x)$. Intensity values above a certain threshold corresponding to a certain percentage of the pixels with the highest intensity values, are classified as anomalies or potential media leakages, in this case. Some morphological operations are applied to areas with pixels

classified as potential leakages and the areas are visualized to the end user, Fig. 5.5d. Additional details can be found in [69].

Another example of a background modelling technique is to use channel representations, previously described in Section 3.4. The technique was employed in Paper C in order to mitigate the problem of background contamination of the object model. Each pixel of the object region is represented by a channel vector and in each frame, the background model is updated according to Eq. 5.1. In Paper C, the background model is only updated in a region around the tracked object in order to reduce the computational cost. The channel representation is favourable for TIR images since it models the distribution of intensity values rather than spatial features, this was also concluded in Paper A. Trackers based on spatial structure were ranked higher on the RGB dataset than the TIR dataset. For the EDFT tracker that is based on channel representations, it was the other way around.

5.2.2 Correlation filters

Adaptive/discriminative correlation filters (DCF's) can be used for a number of different applications. Examples within the field of computer vision are, visual tracking [31, 48, 86], object detection [72, 85], and object alignment [30].

The object detection methods referenced above [72, 85] address detection of specific objects, e.g., pedestrians. DCF's can, however, also be used for unsupervised anomaly detection if the background is repetitive. That is, an anomaly is defined as a failure to detect background. A DCF based approach to unsupervised anomaly detection models the appearance of the background by adaptive, discriminative correlation filters and detection is performed via convolution.

The Convolution Theorem states that correlation becomes an element-wise multiplication in the Fourier domain. Therefore, all filter operations are performed in the Fourier domain using the Fast Fourier Transform in order to reduce computation time. Correlation in the Fourier domain between a filter H and an image patch F takes the form:

$$G = F \odot \overline{H}. \quad (5.2)$$

The bar denotes complex conjugation and \odot represents element-wise multiplication.

DCF based approaches find a filter H that minimizes the sum of squared errors of the difference between the desired output G_j and the convolution $F_j \odot \overline{H}$ for a number of training samples $j \in \{1, \dots, J\}$, i.e.,

$$\min_{\overline{H}} \sum_j \|F_j \odot \overline{H} - G_j\|^2. \quad (5.3)$$

The desired output G_j is the Fourier transform of the ideal filter response, typically a Gaussian with its peak centred at the target. The solution to (5.3) is:

$$\overline{H} = \frac{\sum_j G_j \odot \overline{F_j}}{\sum_j F_j \odot \overline{F_j}}, \quad (5.4)$$

where division is performed element-wise. A complete derivation is given in [31].

The predicted position of the detected object at time t is found at the maximum value of the filter response y_t :

$$y_t = \mathcal{F}^{-1}\{\overline{H}_t Z\}, \quad (5.5)$$

where Z is an image patch of a search area. If new examples of the object are provided and added to the set of training samples, an optimal filter can be obtained by minimizing the output error over the complete set. This approach is, however, not feasible for online learning applications. Instead, the filter is adaptively updated using a weighted average with update factor $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ as

$$H_t = \frac{A_t}{B_t}, \quad (5.6)$$

where

$$A_t = (1 - \alpha) A_{t-1} + \alpha (\overline{G}_{t-1} \odot F_{t-1}), \quad (5.7)$$

$$B_t = (1 - \alpha) B_{t-1} + \alpha (\overline{F}_{t-1} \odot F_{t-1}). \quad (5.8)$$

In order to reduce the problem of zero-frequency components in F leading to division by zero, a regularization parameter λ can be added to Eq. 5.3, see [31].

Paper D utilizes a one-dimensional DCF for anomaly detection. The paper addresses the problem of obstacle detection in front of a train when using thermal imagery from a train-mounted camera. Here, due to the known geometry and repetitive nature of the area between rails, a one-dimensional, horizontal filter is employed. The filter is applied row-wise within a rail mask provided by a preceding rail detection step.

5.2.3 Generative adversarial networks

Unsupervised anomaly detection in high-dimensional data such as images is a challenging problem addressed in recent works [5, 6, 53, 145, 180, 181, 212, 213] (and Paper F). As previously mentioned, distances in high-dimensional data quickly lose discriminative power due to the curse of dimensionality. Through their latent space, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) [78] can model complex, high-dimensional data distributions [44] and are, therefore, suitable for anomaly detection in images.

In their original formulation, GANs do not possess the ability of mapping an observation back to the latent space. GAN-based anomaly detection methods are, therefore, often extended with an addition called an *inference mechanism*. The inference mechanism enables backprojection of image samples onto the latent space. Examples of a few different inference mechanisms have been described in Section 4.5.4.

GAN-based methods learn an implicit distribution of the normal data in contrast to probabilistic methods that learn the distribution explicitly. Therefore, anomaly detection can typically not be performed in the latent space, since this would require backprojection of an unreasonable high number of normal samples (assuming relatively high dimensionality of the latent space). The typical approach of a GAN-based method is, therefore, instead to search for the closest match $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$ of a query image Q in latent space. An anomaly score can then be formulated as the difference between the reconstructed (by the generator) image $\mathcal{G}(\hat{\mathbf{z}})$ and Q by some image similarity measurement. This approach assumes that the generator can generate normal samples but not anomalies, and that the reconstructed closest match $\mathcal{G}(\hat{\mathbf{z}})$ will be an image similar to the query image Q without the anomaly present. Hence, GAN-based methods also provide the ability to detect anomalous *regions*, i.e., localize anomalies within images, in contrast to many classical anomaly detection methods by applying some threshold to the residual image $\mathbf{x}_R = |Q - \mathcal{G}(\hat{\mathbf{z}})|$.

In Paper F, a method for unsupervised anomaly detection based on a Generative Adversarial Network is presented. In contrast to previous methods, the proposed method trains an encoder jointly with the generator employing an encirclement loss, a more detailed description was given in Section 4.5.4. The encirclement loss enforces similar images to lie close to each other also in the latent space. In this stratified latent space, norms of backprojected anomalies are smaller than the norms of backprojected normal samples. The norm can, thus, be used as an additional cue to discriminate anomalous from normal samples.

5.3 Cross-spectral transfer learning

Deep learning techniques, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) in particular, have had great success in a number of different research areas recently. CNNs do, however, often require large amounts of training data in order to be successful. By using transfer learning techniques, it is possible to benefit from the recent advances also when only small amounts of training data is available. Large datasets and/or networks pre-trained on thermal infrared (TIR) images are rare and cross-spectral transfer learning from visual RGB to TIR is, therefore, highly relevant.

Pan et al. [151] define the aims of transfer learning to be the "extraction of knowledge from one or more source tasks followed by application of this

Figure 5.6: (a) The pre-trained model \mathcal{F}_1 maps input samples \mathbf{x}_1 of modality \mathcal{M}_1 to output \mathbf{y} . In order to transfer the knowledge of \mathcal{F}_1 and find a mapping $\mathbf{x}_2 \mapsto \mathbf{y}$ one approach is to (b) finetune the parameters of the model, i.e., $\theta_1 \mapsto \theta_2$. Another approach is to (c) find a mapping $\mathcal{M}_2 \mapsto \mathcal{M}_1$ between the two modalities. The (d) reverse mapping $\mathcal{M}_1 \mapsto \mathcal{M}_2$ is also possible.

knowledge to a target task”. In contrast to *domain adaptation*, where the source and target tasks are required to be equal, transfer learning does not imply any restrictions on either the task or the domain or the amount of labelled target samples. More information on transfer learning and domain adaptation techniques can be found in, for example, [45, 151, 202].

Assuming equal source and target tasks, there are two main approaches to cross-spectral transfer learning, illustrated in Fig. 5.6. A pre-trained model $\mathcal{F}_1(\mathbf{x}_1; \theta_1)$, $\mathcal{F}_1: \mathbf{x}_1 \mapsto \mathbf{y}$ with parameters θ_1 maps input samples \mathbf{x}_1 of modality \mathcal{M}_1 to output \mathbf{y} , Fig. 5.6a. Input samples \mathbf{x}_2 are samples of a different modality (\mathcal{M}_2) and we would like to find a model $\mathcal{F}_2(\mathbf{x}_2; \theta_2)$, $\mathcal{F}_2: \mathbf{x}_2 \mapsto \mathbf{y}$. The first main approach to cross-spectral transfer learning, Fig. 5.6b, is to find a mapping of the model parameters $\theta_1 \mapsto \theta_2$, realized by e.g. *finetuning*, further described in Section 5.3.1. The second approach is to find a mapping between the two modalities $\mathcal{M}_2 \mapsto \mathcal{M}_1$ or $\mathcal{M}_1 \mapsto \mathcal{M}_2$, Fig. 5.6c and 5.6d. Examples of cross-spectral modality transfer techniques are given in Section 5.3.2. After the mapping of \mathbf{x}_2 to modality \mathcal{M}_1 , Fig. 5.6c, the pre-trained model \mathcal{F}_1 can

Figure 5.7: A YOLO9000 object detector applied to thermal infrared images featuring an outdoor biofuel storage. In (a)-(c) there has been no finetuning of the detector. Pink (bed), orange (car), and green (train) boxes are YOLO9000 detections of different classes. In (d)-(f), the YOLO9000 detector was finetuned for the purpose of vehicle detection. The images show successful examples. Pink boxes are YOLO9000 detections of class truck and red boxes are ground truth annotations.

be applied. Another option would be the reverse mapping, $\mathcal{M}_1 \mapsto \mathcal{M}_2$, in order to generate more training data in \mathcal{M}_2 . The model $\mathcal{F}_2 : \mathbf{x}_2 \mapsto \mathbf{y}$ can then be trained from scratch, as illustrated in Fig. 5.6d.

5.3.1 Finetuning

The most common approach to deep transfer learning is to simply freeze all but one or a few of the final layers in a pre-trained network and then retrain it using the target dataset [9]. This approach, known as *finetuning*, is based on the well-known fact that the upper layers of a network are more task specific while the lower layers are more modal specific [120]. Therefore, in the case of cross-spectral transfer learning, this approach might not be the optimal one and different techniques should be examined further.

Some examples of detection results from a default and finetuned YOLO9000 object detector [164] applied to thermal infrared images can be seen in Fig. 5.7. The network was pre-trained on the COCO object detection dataset [126] and default parameters were used. Without finetuning, Fig. 5.7a-5.7c, the detector failed to detect any of the vehicles in the validation dataset. It did, however, provide some interesting results. For example, it could successfully detect a train in the thermal infrared modality, Fig. 5.7c, large piles of biofuel apparently had certain similarities to beds, Fig. 5.7a, and a caravan was labelled as a car, Fig. 5.7b, while the two cars next to it remained undetected. After finetuning the last layer of the detector for the purpose of vehicle detection, detection performance improves. A few successful examples are shown in Fig. 5.7d-5.7f.

These examples provide some insight in the difficulties related to transfer learning from visual RGB to TIR. Deep neural networks, despite their successes, do not by default possess the highly complex modality generalization abilities possessed by the human brain.

5.3.2 Cross-spectral modality transfer

Modality transfer is the process of altering a source domain as an attempt to bring the distribution of the source closer to that of the target. There are multiple objectives for modality transfer, the purpose can, e.g., be transfer learning, as described above, or visualization in order to facilitate interpretation, as in Paper G. In the case of thermal to visual spectrum image transfer, there is no correspondence between the measured thermal radiation of an object and its color, which makes it a challenging problem. It is assumed, however, that there is an underlying semantic representation common to the two modalities and the aim is to find these latent representations.

In Paper G, a dataset with corresponding TIR and visual RGB image pairs enabled semi-supervised learning in the form of an autoencoder network. The acquisition of TIR and visual RGB image pairs with perfect pixel to pixel correspondence is, however, a difficult task. Since glass is opaque in TIR wavelengths, optics for thermal cameras are typically made of materials like germanium. Hence, it is difficult, but not impossible, to acquire thermal and visual images with the same optical axis. A modality transfer method is, therefore, required to be robust to image pair misalignments. In Paper G, the problem is mitigated by separating the loss into a luminance and a chrominance part, exploiting the lower acuity for color differences possessed by the human visual system.

The method proposed in Paper G was the first published approach to TIR to perceptually realistic RGB transfer. The work was later extended by Nyberg et al. [148] who proposed an unsupervised method based on generative adversarial networks for unpaired thermal to visible spectrum transfer. Compared to the method in Paper G, the proposed method does not require image

Figure 5.8: Examples of real-world applications related to the addressed problems. Image courtesy of ^{*}Termisk Systemteknik AB, [†]Agricam AB, and [◊]Imafor AB. [‡]Reproduced with the permission of Springer.

pairs with pixel to pixel correspondence and the resulting visual spectrum images were sharper.

5.4 Relevance to real-world applications

In this chapter, three different problems have been described in the context of image analysis in thermal infrared (TIR) images. There are many real-world applications related to automatic image analysis in TIR images and to the addressed problems in particular. As TIR image resolution and quality increase and prices decrease there will be even more, not even thought of yet.

5.4.1 Visual object tracking

Visual object tracking is a general problem relevant to a number of different areas, for example, surveillance, robotics, autonomous driving, automation, and medicine. Examples include tracking of objects in various **research** projects, e.g., tracking and counting bats emerging from a cave [91]. Other examples are tracking of pedestrians in systems for **automotive safety**, using a small thermal camera mounted in the front of a car (or train) (Paper D) [28, 214], Fig. 5.8b, and **search and rescue**, searching for persons independently of daylight using cameras carried by UAVs, helicopters or rescue robots [170].

Tracking methods can also be used within **agriculture** for monitoring of wild and domestic animals in order to e.g. perform behaviour analysis, or to estimate population sizes [73, 91]. For **security** applications, detection, tracking, and behaviour analysis of persons and vehicles can be applied for the purpose of detection of intrusions and suspicious behaviour (Paper C) [52, 101], Fig. 5.8f.

5.4.2 Anomaly detection

The general nature of the formulation of the anomaly detection problem makes it applicable to a range of different fields. For example, problems within the field of **agriculture** such as detection of diseases in plants [163] or detection of inflammations in dairy cows [41], Fig. 5.8a. Other examples include problems within **industry**, e.g., detection of different materials, positioning, and non-destructive testing (Paper E) [144, 171], Fig. 5.8d.

Thermal (radiometric) cameras can also be useful for **fire detection** since they can see through smoke, Fig. 5.8c. They are commonly used by fire fighters to find persons and to localise the base of the fire [155, 173]. For **medical** applications, thermal infrared cameras can be used for detection of tumours in early stages, inflammations, fever screening, etc. [3, 38, 114], Fig. 5.8e.

5.4.3 Cross-spectral modality transfer

Learning methods such as deep neural networks usually require large amounts of training data. As described in Section 5.3.2, cross-spectral modality transfer is highly relevant for scarcely used image modalities such as thermal infrared. These methods, thus, enable application of pre-trained models on visual images onto, e.g., thermal infrared images. In summary, real-world applications that benefit from the TIR modality due to, e.g., operation during night can make use of methods pre-trained for the visual modality without requiring annotation of large amounts of training data.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

This thesis has addressed the problem of automatic image analysis in thermal infrared images with a focus on machine learning methods. The main purpose has been to study the variations of processing required due to the thermal infrared modality. In particular, three different problems have been addressed: visual object tracking, anomaly detection, and modality transfer. This chapter concludes the thesis by discussing the results, suggesting directions for future work, and describing its impact on society.

6.1 Conclusions and discussion

In this thesis, the variations of processing required due to the thermal infrared (TIR) modality have been studied from a few different directions. Even though each one of the included publications has a quite narrow problem formulation, they are all part of the overall aim of the thesis. Common to most of the included papers is the usage of machine learning methods. It can be concluded that the specification to thermal infrared images often lies in the representation, or design of the loss function, rather than the machine learning method itself. Some exceptions presumably exist, one example could, for example, be in the design of a CNN, see future work.

A thermal infrared camera measures the thermal infrared radiation, i.e., radiation *beyond the visible spectrum*, within an area. The differences between thermal infrared and visible imagery have been explained in this thesis. For example, in the noise characteristics, the amount of discernible spatial patterns, the data format, and how the emitted radiation behave in comparison to reflected radiation.

Some of the common challenges to image analysis methods when applied to visual images, e.g., rapid illumination changes and shadows, do not exist in thermal infrared (TIR) images. On the other hand, it is usually, for example, more difficult to discriminate between different objects in TIR since visual

color patterns are discernible in TIR only if they correspond to variations in material or temperature. In conclusion, image analysis in TIR compared to visual images is more simple in some aspects and more complicated in others.

Within the last couple of years, there has been many published works within the computer vision field where standard methods designed for visual images have been applied directly to thermal infrared images. The methods are often applied without considering the differences between the two modalities. As has been shown in this thesis, methods designed for visual images might be suboptimal for TIR for several reasons. For example, these methods are often designed to be invariant to illumination changes, a phenomenon that does not exist in thermal infrared images.

Finally, it is of the author's belief that the included publications have raised awareness of the problems related to image analysis in thermal infrared images compared to visual images. Especially through the published benchmark, leading to the challenges VOT-TIR 2015 and 2016, raising the standard for publicly available thermal infrared tracking benchmarks.

6.2 Future work

This thesis have focused on three problems within the field of computer vision for thermal infrared images: visual object tracking, anomaly detection, and modality transfer. There are many other aspects of the overall goal to study the variations of processing required that have not been addressed here. In addition, there are aspects and parts of the addressed problems that could be examined further. In the remainder of this section, a few of these are discussed.

The VOT-TIR 2015 benchmark compared trackers participating both in the visual tracking challenge VOT and the thermal infrared challenge VOT-TIR. Since the visual and thermal datasets were completely unrelated, the comparison could only be made by an examination of the relative ratings of the different trackers. Future work could be to construct a large, fully synchronized RGB and TIR dataset for tracking evaluation. Comparing tracking result on RGB and TIR could provide insight on what features of a tracker that are important for RGB and TIR respectively. In particular, frame-wise labels of visual attributes, e.g., camera motion, occlusion etc. could provide further insight. The VOT-RGBT 2019 benchmark had a multi-modal RGB-T dataset, the synchronization was, however, not perfect and the challenge was joint RGB and TIR tracking.

The semi-automatic annotation method proposed in Paper B could be improved. One suggestion is to incorporate frame-wise labels of visual attributes in order to prevent the failure detection method to get stuck in occlusion areas.

Concerning Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) trained on TIR images it should be examined further what features are learnt by the filters in

comparison to CNNs trained on visual images. There are many publications [56, 120, 132, 209, 211] that visualizes and examines what happens at the different nodes and layers, what filters that are learnt etc. for visual images, but not for the thermal infrared modality.

There are several special cases not addressed in Paper D that could be addressed in future work, e.g., heated railroad switches and connecting railroads. Furthermore, the railroad detection could possibly be aided by the incorporation of a GPS and access to a railroad map.

Regarding anomaly detection by Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), a more extensive examination of the structure of the latent space, especially in the case when an encirclement loss and encoder is introduced, is needed. Other ways to structure the latent space for the purpose of anomaly detection should be further examined as well. It has been shown that GANs indeed do not copy training samples but rather learns the distribution, e.g., by Karras et al. [102]. The percentage of anomalies in the training data that can be included before the GAN includes them in the learnt distribution should be investigated. Further work is also to apply the method proposed in Paper F to thermal infrared, or multi-spectral images. For example, the method could be applied to the problem of district heating leakage detection discussed in Paper E.

Finally, this thesis barely scratches upon the topic of transfer learning techniques between different modalities. An area that should be investigated further since it is highly relevant. For scarcely used modalities such as thermal infrared, manual annotation is difficult to justify and only a few fully annotated large-scale datasets exist.

6.3 Impact on society

The popularity of thermal cameras have increased in recent years as image resolution and quality have increased in combination with a decrease in camera price and size. Thermal cameras are advantageous to visual cameras in many applications due to their ability to see in total darkness, their robustness to illumination changes, and less intrusion on privacy. In the future, they will be even more common in civilian applications than they are today.

Many applications connected to thermal cameras can be related to a sustainable society, for example, prevention and localisation of energy losses, as well as environmental friendly transportation. Areas that are highly relevant in today's society.

Privacy-preserving techniques will become more important as cameras become increasingly common in our every day lives. Thermal infrared imaging is considered to be a technique that preserves the privacy of humans and will, thus, play an important role.

As technology evolves, the human-machine interface will become more important. Modality transfer techniques for the purpose of visualization will facilitate the interpretation for those that are not an expert on the specific modality.

Finally, some of the methods covered in this thesis are already used in real-world applications today, making an impact on society by detecting intrusions, preventing fires, and detecting district heating leakages.

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PART II

PUBLICATIONS

Publications

The publications associated with this thesis have been removed for copyright reasons. For more details about these see:

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**Thermal radiation interpreted
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